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EDITORIAL

Echoes of Wisdom: Bridging Historical Insight with Contemporary Discourse in the Modern Era

We live in the era of rapid technological advancement and societal transformation. This has made past intellectual resources of the world available. To bridge the wisdom of the past with the challenges of the present becomes easy. Our understanding of the world has always been deeply rooted in the traditions, philosophies, and theories developed by thinkers across centuries. Yet, as we navigate the complexities of today, it becomes increasingly clear that these ancient insights are not relics of a bygone era but living tools that can guide us toward innovative solutions for tomorrow's challenges.

In this issue of the Journal of Creative Writing, Volume 7, Issue 1, we celebrate the scholarly contributions that seamlessly blend historical wisdom with contemporary discourse, offering fresh perspectives on issues that continue to shape our world.

The first article, "The Impact of the Multimodal Approach to EAP Courses," explores the evolving landscape of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) instruction. This research underscores the importance of integrating diverse

modalities to enhance learning experience, reflecting a need to adapt educational practices to the realities of a globally connected, digital world. The author's insights remind us that effective communication in academia transcends traditional boundaries and is rooted in a holistic approach to language learning.

Next, in "The Influence of British Colonization on English as a Lingua Franca in Africa," the author delves into the historical and ongoing effects of British colonialism on language dynamics in Africa. This article illuminates the enduring impact of colonization on linguistic practices, demonstrating how historical forces continue to shape contemporary communication across the continent. By revisiting the past, the author provides a critical lens through which we can understand and address the linguistic inequalities that persist today.

In "Bridging Centuries: Al-Mawardi's Philosophy in Modern Governance," the author brings the 11th-century Islamic scholar Al-Mawardi's theories into conversation with modern governance practices. This article exemplifies how ancient political philosophy can offer valuable insights into the governance challenges of the 21st century, providing a framework that is both timeless and timely. The author's work encourages us to look beyond the surface of contemporary issues, drawing from deep philosophical wells to inform practical solutions.

"The Paradigmatic Theory of Al-Mawardi" further explores the contributions of this influential thinker, highlighting how his paradigms continue to resonate in today's socio-political context. This piece not only pays homage to Al-Mawardi's intellectual legacy but also emphasizes the relevance of classical theories in addressing current and future challenges in governance and societal organization.

"Exploring the Challenges Faced by Learners and Teachers in English Versions" addresses the educational hurdles encountered in English-medium instruction. The article provides a critical analysis of the barriers to effective learning and teaching in such settings, offering solutions that are informed by both modern pedagogical theory and an understanding of the cultural contexts

in which these challenges arise. This research is a testament to the ongoing need for culturally responsive educational practices that honor the diverse experiences of learners.

Finally, in “Relevance of Islamic Traditional Pedagogical Strategies in 21st Century Education: A Case Study of Al-Qarawiyyin University,” the authors examine the enduring value of traditional teaching methods in a modern educational context. This study focuses on Al-Qarawiyyin University, the world’s oldest academic institution, and investigates how its adherence to conventional pedagogy continues to benefit intellectual and personal development in the 21st century. The authors argue that the traditional approach nurtures close relationships between teachers and students, encourages critical thinking, and promotes skills that are just as relevant today as they were centuries ago. This article invites us to reconsider the place of time-honored educational strategies in an age dominated by technological innovation.

As we present these scholarly works, we acknowledge and celebrate the authors’ dedication to their craft. Their contributions not only enhance our understanding of the past and present but also pave the way for future research and innovation. Each article in this issue is a testament to the power of creative and critical thinking, demonstrating that by engaging with the theories and philosophies of yesterday, we can develop meaningful solutions for today and tomorrow.

We hope this collection inspires further inquiry and dialogue, encouraging our readers to explore the intersections between historical wisdom and contemporary challenges. Together, let us continue to bring the rich traditions of the past into the heart of today’s academic and creative endeavors, forging a path toward a more informed and thoughtful future.

Dr. Tareq M Zayed
Editor

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THE IMPACT OF USING THE MULTIMODAL APPROACH IN ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSE COURSES: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the implications of a multimodal approach to teaching EAP courses, with a focus on a private university in Bangladesh, and whether this approach would improve learners' attitudes toward learning English. An effective experiment was designed and presented to two groups of undergraduate learners at the Green University of Bangladesh to measure the impact of multimodal approach in teaching learning of English. To begin, one group of learners was taught English using a traditional approach, whereas the other group was taught English using a multimodal approach in their English for Academic Purpose courses. Total 90 learners from both groups and two instructors of the course 'English for Academic Purpose' in each group took part in this experimental study. The results of this experiment revealed that learners in the English for Academic Purpose course

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prefer to use variety of modes and semiotic resources simultaneously to better grasp a lesson. Based on the participants' suggestions, this study concludes that the multimodal approach is preferable to the conventional technique.

KEYWORDS: Multinomial approach; multimodality in learning; modes; semiotic resources; multimodal text

INTRODUCTION

The teachers of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) in private universities need to focus on implementing various modes. However, they often rush through documents or materials to meet institutional syllabus requirements within a designated timeframe. In the rapidly evolving landscape of education, learners are distancing themselves from traditional approaches. Despite this shift, many instructors in private educational institutions pay insufficient attention to the needs of the new generation. In an effective EAP class, instructors should prioritize spending a significant amount of time on teaching, observing learners, noting their needs, and ultimately finding standardized solutions through the utilization of various modes and the application of blended techniques with diverse semiotic resources. These activities exemplify the Multimodal approach (Marchetti & Cullen, 2016). Despite its time-consuming nature, instructors often overlook the importance of this approach. Furthermore, learners in EAP courses frequently focus on preparing for tests rather than acquiring a deeper understanding of language usage. The Multimodal approach plays a crucial role, yet its implementation is scarce within the classroom, especially in EAP courses offered by private universities in Bangladesh. This scarcity arises from teachers' rough and ambiguous assumptions about this approach, creating a substantial gap in the teaching process.

A multimodal approach offers support to learners in navigating the challenges encountered within the classroom environment. Moreover, through the integration of multimodality, learners can create conducive situations that foster enjoyable and expedited learning experiences. Despite a body of research underscoring the significance of this approach across various educational fields, the educational landscape in Bangladesh, particularly in the

present era, predominantly witnesses the adoption of a singular approach by teachers. This singular approach poses challenges for learners in terms of the learning process. Consequently, the incorporation of multimodality emerges as a beneficial strategy for addressing the diverse array of challenges confronted by English for Academic Purposes (EAP) learners (Marchetti & Cullen, 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

What is Multimodal Approach in Teaching

Multimodality in teaching refers to the interdependence of various communication modes to complete a communicative process (Ting, 2013). The pedagogical approach to multimodal language learning involves utilizing digital technologies to teach or learn a language through texts, images, audios, videos, and multimedia (Lotherington & Jenson, 2011). Kress and van Leeuwen (2001, p.20) define multimodality as the use of multiple semiotic modes in the design of a semiotic product, with a specific emphasis on the combination of these modes. Each modality covers different aspects of phenomena, challenging prior conceptions and providing resources for imagination and critical thinking (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2001). The capability to consume, interpret, and produce multimodal literacies is increasingly significant for academic and social purposes (Jewitt & Kress, 2003; Yi, 2014).

The term ‘multimodality’ commonly describes practices and resources in contemporary digitally mediated literacy, particularly from a social semiotics perspective, where ‘mode’ is viewed as a culturally and socially fashioned resource for representation and communication (Kress, 2003: 45). A multimodal approach is considered a source of modernity and creativity for both teachers and learners, drawing upon visual, audio, and kinesthetic modes to engage learners in the course content (Laadem & Mallahi, 2019). Despite its benefits, the acceptance of multimodality for teaching and learning has been hindered by traditional views of linguistically based literacy and language (Hundley & Holbrook, 2013). Integrating multimodal approaches in ESL teaching has the potential to enhance learners’ autonomy, motivation, and

accommodate various learning styles (Ganapathy & Seetharam, 2016).

To meet the demands of a rapidly changing society, colleges and universities should acknowledge the limitations of traditional English teaching and actively innovate through various effective ways to cultivate talents that align with social development needs (Wu, 2020). Kress, a key contributor to social semiotic multimodal theory, highlights the affordances of different modes in terms of materiality, emphasizing the unique potentials for representation offered by time-based and space-based modes (Kress 2003: 45). Learners perceive multimodal task designs as enjoyable (Korkealehto & Leire, 2019), and the presentation of multiple input sources affects attentional demands and underlying cognitive processes (sánchez, 2022). The integration of technology in education has elevated the standard of educational materials (Esky, 2019).

Multimodality is a burgeoning academic field studied by researchers from diverse disciplines, including linguistics, literature, communication, visual arts, design, media studies, health sciences, engineering, anthropology, jewelry and fashion design, and information technology. Researchers aim to identify challenges and opportunities in using multimodal approaches to pedagogy in diverse and developing contexts, as exemplified by South Africa (Archer & Newfield, 2014).

The current generation of learners, known as Digital Natives, has grown up in a technology-filled environment and is adaptable to changes, being accustomed to ICT language (Prensky, 2001, as cited in Carroll, 2011). Recent case studies on the effects of multimodal literacy have demonstrated substantial learning among learners exposed to a variety of multimodal tasks related to reading and writing (Walsh, 2010).

Implications of Multimodal Approach in Language Teaching

In the realm of language education, the multimodal approach elucidates the significance of employing diverse semiotic resources, utilizing various modes tailored to learners' strategies and needs in different circumstances. This approach has become standard in the 21st century, encompassing four primary methods: visual, auditory, reading and writing, and kinesthetic (VARK). The

multimodal learning style, integrating multiple communication inputs, proves more effective, utilizing various modes to engage learners. This method involves employing multiple modes, which function as distinct learning channels, leveraging senses such as visual and auditory to address challenges and overcome learners' psychological barriers. Multimodality represents a universal and supportive learning approach, catering to diverse learning requirements by employing efficient communication concepts. This involves simultaneous use of text and audio for reading and listening support, captivating learners through images and scenarios, and providing examples for enhanced comprehension. Using these diverse semiotic resources supports learners, emphasizing the adoption of various modes based on learners' different learning capacities or knowledge levels.

Furthermore, multimodal learning contributes to children's proficiency enhancement and skill development. Numerous studies highlight the effectiveness of multimodal learning, particularly in combining text and visuals for improved learning outcomes. This approach creates a positive and conducive learning environment, advocating for individualized pedagogy to ensure every learner's success in concept clarity. Multimodal texts, serving as composite communication figures, embody various modes, resembling multimedia models that employ different components such as vocabulary, pictures, and sounds to enrich learners' knowledge.

In the contemporary era, where technology plays an integral role in daily life, it can be a valuable semiotic resource in the multimodal approach. Technology facilitates easier learning and teaching, making both teachers and learners active participants. Serving as part of multimodal approach's semiotic resources, technology provides materials with up-to-date information, enabling learners to stay abreast of regular changes and updates while stimulating multiple meanings simultaneously.

The multimodal approach acts as a source of creativity within the classroom, fostering creativity for both instructors and learners. It centers on composing a survey and narrating a comprehensive collection of meaning-making assets utilized by instructors in diverse domains and learning contexts,

ensuring the development of technical meaning that demonstrates their incorporation to create meaning. Overall, the multimodal approach enriches the language learning experience and skill development by incorporating diverse materials that empower learners with extensive opportunities for multimodal learning.

How to Apply Multimodal Method in Teaching

The multimodal approach entails the integration of various modes, and its application to language teaching emphasizes the creative combination of text, audio, and image as distinct modes. This integration is aimed at generating meaning and fostering interaction and learning within the classroom context (Marchetti & Cullen, 2016, p.39). Unlike general English courses, English for Academic Purposes (EAP) courses predominantly focus on instructing learners in formal and academic language genres, rather than conventional and social genres (Hamp-Lyons, 2001).

In the 1990s, Western scholars introduced multimodal theory, proposing the use of diverse semiotic resources, such as sound, images, video, animation, motion, color, and facial expressions, to engage learners' senses and enhance learning efficiency (Pan and Zhang, 2020). Leveraging multimodal and multimedia resources can significantly contribute to enhancing multimodal communication practices in English language teaching within higher education (Crawford Camiciottoli and Campoy-Cubillo, 2018). This perspective aligns with the idea that 'knowledge is multimodal, co-constructed, and performed or represented' (Miller, 2007, p. 65).

A multimodal approach in the classroom serves as a wellspring of creativity for both educators and learners. It taps into available visual, audio, and kinesthetic modes and is not contingent on technology, offering a versatile and innovative means of instruction (Marchetti & Cullen, 2015).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research attempts to identify the perceptions of teachers and learners about the implementation of the multimodal approach to examine the impact of using the multimodal approach in EAP courses. Thus this study has the

following three research objectives:

1. To examine the impact of using Multimodal approach in EAP courses on Learners.
2. To find out the usefulness Multimodal approach for teaching and learning English language.
3. To compare instructor's engagement in traditional teaching and multimodal teaching.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study aimed at scrutinizing and assessing the research through the analysis of data gathered from pre-test and post-test surveys, along with an observation checklist. The research design adopted was of a quantitative nature, allowing for the generation of numerical data and empirical insights using statistical and logical techniques.

Research Settings

This experimental investigation was conducted within the classrooms of Green University of Bangladesh. A control group consisting of 45 learners and an experimental group with an equal number were observed during their participation in the “English for Academic Purpose” course, where both traditional and multimodal teaching approaches were employed.

Participants

The study involved a total of 90 undergraduate participants enrolled in the “English for Academic Purpose (EAP-101)” course. As part of the experimental design, both groups underwent a pre-test and post-test, facilitated by a questionnaire. The participants were initially divided into two sections: Section A, comprising 45 learners as the control group, and Section B, consisting of 45 learners as the experimental group. This resulted in a total of 90 participants, all of whom completed both pre-test and post-test survey questionnaires. Additionally, an observation survey spanned three months, involving around 90 learners and two instructors who were observed during classes.

While choosing participants, components such as gender diversity, different

types of personality, aptitude, hobbies, and so on were not taken into consideration for this experimental study. Distribution of participants is given below in detail (Table 1 and 2):

Table 1: Distribution of Pre-Test / Post-Test Participants

Data Collection Techniques	No. of Participants in the Control Group	No. of Participants in the Experimental Group	Total
Pre- test Survey	45	45	90
Post- test Survey	45	45	90

Table 2: Distribution of Participants of observation

Data Elicitation Techniques	No. of Participants in the Control Group		No. of Participants in the Experimental Group		Total	
	Learners	Teacher	Learners	Teacher	Learners	Instructor/Teacher
Observation checklist →	45	1	45	1	90	2

Research Instruments

The researcher developed an instrument based on multimodal activities and teaching-learning practices. The questionnaire statements can be found in the analysis section of this paper.

Data Collection Procedure

The data collection procedure was organized in various ways. Pre-test and post-test data from both participant groups were utilized to assess the distinctions between the two approaches. Additionally, during the application of interventions in both traditional and multimodal classes, observational data were collected through the researcher's presence.

Data Analysis Methods

Quantitative analysis, exclusively involving descriptive and simple statistical methods, was employed for data analysis in this research. The pre-test questionnaire gathered data in the form of multiple-choice questions, and numerical data were analyzed in MS Excel to generate pie charts and graphs. Percentages were then tabulated.

Results from the Experimental Group

The pre-test and post-test questionnaires were administered separately to participants in both the experimental and control groups. A detailed summary of the pre-test and post-test results from the experimental group is provided in Table 3 for reference.

Table 3: Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Experimental Group

Indicators of Assessment	Results							
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
1. Do you feel comfortable in learning English?	Yes		Partially		No		-	
	15%	45%	35%	32%	50%	23%	-	-
2. What type of mode do you prefer in learning English?	Visual and auditorial learning		Kinesthetic learning (constructing physical activity- play a role of a character)		Learning through reading and writing		All of them	
	35%	17%	10%	9%	50%	16%	5%	65%
3. Where do you see your English Language skill level?	Basic		Good		Advance		Need improvement	
	27%	11%	12%	42%	13%	25%	48%	22%

Indicators of Assessment	Results							
4. How can you improve your English Language skill?	Through watching movies		participating in reading and writing contest		Practical implementation		All of them	
	18%	11%	27%	21%	39%	29%	16%	39%
5. Do you know about Multimodality?	Yes		Partially		No			
	11%	46%	26%	38%	63%	16%	-	-
6. What type of significance is using for learning English in your classroom?	Audio and video		Graded books (books that have simple level of language) and articles		Involving technology for better understanding and practical		All of them	
	17%	13%	56%	22%	19%	11%	8%	54%
7. Learning should be in a particular way or in several ways, what do you think?	One way		Several ways		-		-	
	56%	14%	44%	86%	-	-	-	-
8. How can you justify your self as an English Language listener and speaker?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	23%	36%	11%	8%	32%	42%	34%	14%
9. How can you justify your self as an English Language reader and writer?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	22%	32%	13%	8%	39%	51%	21%	9%

10. Is English Language learning enjoyable?	Yes		Partially			No		-
	13%	36%	29%	53%	58%	11%	-	-

The analysis of pre-test and post-test results (Table 3), expressed as percentages, clearly highlights the substantial impact of a multimodal approach on learners. In the pre-test, the experimental group responded to 10 closed-ended questions, including the query, “Do you feel comfortable in learning English?” During the pre-test, 15% indicated comfort, 35% partial comfort, and 50% discomfort. After implementing the multimodal approach, 45% felt comfortable, 32% partially comfortable, and 23% remained uncomfortable.

Regarding the preferred learning mode for English, 35% initially favored visual and auditory learning, 10% kinesthetic, 50% reading and writing, and 5% a combination. Post-test results revealed shifts, with 17% preferring visual and auditory, 9% kinesthetic, 16% reading and writing, and 65% endorsing a blended approach.

Participants were asked to assess their English language skill levels, with 27% describing their skills as basic, 12% as good, 13% as advanced, and 48% needing improvement in the pre-test. Post-test results showed improvements, with 11% at a basic level, 42% at a good level, 25% at an advanced level, and 22% needing improvement.

Preferences for improving English skills included watching movies (18%), participating in reading and writing contests (27%), practical implementation (39%), and a combination of these (16%). Post-test results demonstrated shifts, with 11% favoring movies, 21% contests, 29% practical implementation, and 39% endorsing all options.

Regarding awareness of multimodality, 11% were initially knowledgeable, 26% partially, and 63% unaware. Post-test results indicated an increase in awareness, with 46% knowledgeable, 38% partially, and 16% unaware.

In terms of significance for learning English in the classroom, 17% initially cited audio and video, 56% graded books and articles, 19% technology, and 8% all. Post-test results showed changes, with 13% favoring audio and video, 22% graded books and articles, 11% technology, and 54% endorsing all modes.

Opinions on learning approaches indicated that 56% preferred a one-way approach, while 44% favored a blended technique. Post-test results showed a shift, with 14% supporting a one-way approach and 86% endorsing several approaches.

Participants' self-assessment of English language proficiency in listening and speaking indicated that 23% considered themselves good, 11% bad, 32% average, and 34% needing improvement initially. Post-test result showed improvements, with 36% considering themselves good, 8% bad, 42% average, and 14% needing improvement.

In terms of reading and writing, 27% initially considered themselves good, 13% bad, 39% average, and 21% needing improvement. Post-test results indicated improvements, with 32% considering themselves good, 8% bad, 51% average, and 9% needing improvement.

Regarding the enjoyment of English language learning, 13% initially found it enjoyable, 29% partially enjoyable, and 58% not enjoyable. Post-test results showed increased enjoyment, with 36% finding it enjoyable, 53% partially enjoyable, and 11% not enjoying, mainly among irregular attendees.

In conclusion, the outcomes of the pre and post-tests (Table 3) underscore the preference for the multimodal approach over the traditional one.

Results from the Control Group

The learners in the control group were administered pre-test and post-test questionnaires. A detailed summary of the pre-test and post-test outcomes for the control group is provided in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Pre-Test and Post-Test Results of Control Group

Area of Assessment	Results							
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
1. Do you feel comfortable in learning English?	Yes		Partially		No		-	
	15 %	17%	35%	39%	50%	44%	-	-
2. What type of mode do you prefer in learning English?	Visual and auditorial learning		Kinesthetic learning (constructing physical activity- play a role of a character)		Learning through reading and writing		All of them	
	35 %	32%	10%	15%	50%	46%	5%	7%
3. Where do you see your English Language skill level?	Basic		Good		Advance		Need improvement	
	27 %	22%	12%	14%	13%	13%	48%	51%
4. How can you improve your English Language skill?	Through watching movies		participating in reading and writing contest		Practical implementat ion		All of them	
	18 %	15%	27%	29%	39%	37%	16%	19%
5. Do you know about Multimodality?	Yes		Partially		No			
	11%	13%	26%	27%	63%	60%	-	-

6. What type of significance is using for learning English in your classroom?	Audio and video		Graded books (books that have simple level of language) and articles		Involving technology for better understanding and practical		All of them	
	17%	16%	56%	52%	19%	20%	8%	12%
7. Learning should be in a particular way or in several ways, what do you think?	One way		Several ways		-		-	
	56%	52%	44%	48%	-	-	-	-
8. How can you justify yourself as an English Language listener and speaker?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	23%	25%	11%	8%	32%	39%	34%	28%
9. How can you justify yourself as an English Language reader and writer?	Good		Bad		Average		Need improvement	
	27%	29%	13%	10%	39%	46%	21%	15%
10. Is English guage learning enjoyable?	Yes		Partially			No		-
	13%	13%	29%	31%	58%	56%	-	-

The identical set of pre-test and post-test questionnaires was administered to the control group, yielding comparable results (Table 4). However, the outcomes for the control group diverged from those of the experimental group. In the pre-test, approximately 15% of learners felt comfortable learning English, which increased marginally to 17% in the post-test. Meanwhile, 35% were partially comfortable in the pre-test, rising to 39% in the post-test. Those not comfortable decreased from 50% in the pre-test to 44% in the post-test, indicating similarities in the control group’s pre-test and post-test outcomes

under the traditional approach.

Regarding learning modes, around 35% preferred visual and auditory methods in the pre-test, 10% favored kinesthetic learning, 50% leaned towards reading and writing, and only 5% preferred all modes. Post-test preferences shifted slightly: 32% favored visual and auditory methods, 15% kinesthetic learning, 46% reading and writing, and 7% favored all modes concurrently.

In terms of English language proficiency, 27% claimed basic skills in the pre-test, 12% had good skills, 13% considered themselves advanced, and 48% identified areas for improvement. Post-test responses mirrored these percentages, indicating consistent outcomes.

Responses to the question “How can you improve your English language skill?” revealed that 18% preferred watching movies, 27% advocated participating in reading and writing contests, 39% favored practical implementation, and 16% chose all options. Post-test results aligned with these percentages.

Multimodality awareness in the control group saw a slight increase from 11% in the pre-test to 13% in the post-test, with 26% and 27% knowing it partially, and 63% and 60% having no knowledge in the pre-test and post-test, respectively.

Regarding the significance attributed to learning English, 17% in the pre-test and 16% in the post-test selected audio and video, 56% and 52% chose graded books and articles, 19% in both tests emphasized the involvement of technology, and 8% and 12% indicated the utilization of all options.

A majority (56%) of learners believed one-way learning was effective for acquiring English language skills, while 44% preferred multiple approaches. Post-test responses remained consistent with these proportions.

Self-assessment of language skills revealed that 23% considered themselves good speakers and listeners, 27% good readers and writers, 11% bad at both, 13% bad readers and writers, 32% average, 39% average readers

and writers, and 34% and 21% acknowledged a definite need for improvement. In the post-test, 25% deemed themselves good speakers and listeners, 8% as deficient, 39% at an average level, and 28% indicating a need for improvement.

Regarding enjoyment, 13% of control group learners found learning English enjoyable in both tests, 29% partially enjoyed it in the pre-test, increasing to 31% in the post-test, and 58% in the pre-test and 56% in the post-test expressed a lack of enjoyment. These consistent results failed to demonstrate contradictions between pre-test and post-test outcomes.

Result of the Learners' Observation

In this empirical investigation, the researcher conducts an observational analysis to examine the level of student engagement in the classroom over the entire session. The observations were systematically conducted in both the control and experimental group classrooms during each session. Specific observation criteria were employed to assess the performance of both learners and instructors in these classrooms. The outcomes are presented in the following table (Table 5):

Table 5: Observation checklist of learner's engagement inside the classroom (experimental group & control group)

SL	Observation	Engagement of the learners inside the classroom (checklist)					
		Always		Sometimes		Never	
		Co	ex	co	ex	Co	Ex
1	full attention during session	29%	62%	22%	27%	49%	11%
2	Involving into pair/group discussions	19%	78%	24%	22%	57%	-
3	Asks questions if they have any requirement for better understanding	3%	58%	16%	31%	81%	11%
4	Follows the instructions of the session	11%	81%	32%	12%	57%	7%

5	Self-motivating via using different modes for better understanding	6%	68%	12%	17%	82%	15%
6	Completing the given multimodal task	10%	78%	26%	11%	64%	11%
7	Willing to participate into conversation for information	-	37%	15%	56%	85%	7%
8	Willing to share their own knowledge with others	-	44%	9%	53%	91%	3%
9	Gives and gets feedback	16%	49%	23%	42%	61%	9%
10	Encourages themselves to perform in front of whole class with full of confidence	-	53%	11%	42%	89%	5%

The researcher utilized a meticulously crafted “Engagement of the Learners inside the Classroom Checklist” to make specific key observations throughout each class session, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the context. This checklist not only aided in identifying crucial inquiries but also served as a valuable tool for tracking learner performance within the classroom.

In the control group, approximately 29% of learners consistently paid full attention during sessions, while 62% of learners in the experimental group demonstrated similar attentiveness. Conversely, 27% and 49% of learners in the control group never paid full attention during sessions, compared to 27% and 11% in the experimental group who sometimes or never paid attention, respectively.

Regarding pair/group discussions, a notable disparity existed between the control and experimental groups. In the control group, 19% always, 24% sometimes, and 57% never engaged in discussions. In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated higher involvement, with 78% always and 22% sometimes participating, while none of the learners refrained from group discussions.

When it came to asking questions for better understanding, only 3% of

control group learners consistently inquired, while 81% never asked questions. In the experimental group, 58% always expressed a willingness to ask questions, 31% did so occasionally, and only 11% refrained from asking, predominantly attributed to irregular attendance.

In following instructions, 11% of control group learners always adhered to instructions, whereas a notable 81% of the experimental group demonstrated consistent adherence. In the control group, 32% sometimes followed instructions, and 57% did not, creating a significant gap in learning. Conversely, in the experimental group, 81% always, 12% sometimes, and only 7% never followed instructions in the EAP course classroom. This comparative discussion contributes to the study's outcome.

Results From Instructors' Observation

Teachers in both classroom groups strive to implement their respective approaches effectively to facilitate learning in their unique ways. However, a substantial disparity exists between the teaching methods employed by teachers in each classroom. In this study, the researcher scrutinizes not only the students' learning approaches but also the teaching methodologies employed by teachers, aiming to anticipate the outcomes in each group. The results of the observation checklists, conducted over a three-month period for all classes, are quantified as percentages and presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Observation checklist of Instructors' Teaching Procedure inside the classroom (experimental group & control group)

SL	Criteria/ statement/ learning activities	Level					
		Yes		Partially		No	
		Co	Ex	Co	Ex	Co	Ex
1	Creating scope for brainstorm	19%	64%	21%	36%	60%	-
2	Adding different media	16%	58%	27%	39%	57%	3%
3	Avoiding the monotonous environment with blended learning techniques	13%	65%	24%	27%	63%	8%
4	Constructing multimodal tasks	5%	78%	12%	22%	83%	-

5	Using texts that includes visual concept	8%	69%	17%	25%	75%	6%
6	Teaching concepts through multiple modes	9%	68%	19%	25%	72%	7%
7	Teaching a content using different Semiotic resources	8%	74%	27%	22%	65%	4%
8	Providing feedback through different media	-	55%	14%	42%	86%	13%
9	Letting learners organize their thoughts in flowcharts diagrams or graphs and explain key concepts with illustrations or pictures	-	49%	20%	39%	80%	12%
10	Teaching major concepts repeatedly with the help of modes	-	67%	26%	29%	74%	4%
11	Encouraging group discussions or debates while learning inside the classroom	9%	59%	22%	36%	69%	5%
12	Using body language gesture and sample or models to explain major concepts with real life examples or scenarios	6%	50%	11%	41%	83%	9%
13	Organizing such situation to experiment or implement the application that learners are learning	-	52%	22%	37%	78%	11%
14	Assigning multimedia presentations, projects, or case studies	19%	70%	27%	30%	54%	-
15	Involving visual, aural, reading writing and kinesthetic learning at the same time to provide a clear concept about the content	-	79%	30%	21%	70%	-

DISCUSSION

This study underscores the robust effectiveness of the Multimodal approach in the “English for Academic Purpose” (EAP) classroom, demonstrating its ability to enhance learners’ English language acquisition by improving multiple skills simultaneously through diverse modes and semiotic resources. Survey results highlight the paramount importance of adopting multiple modes, revealing that the Multimodal approach is particularly beneficial for encouraging differently abled learners. The participants, divided into control and experimental groups, demonstrated significant differences in their responses after undergoing the experiment. While the control group, adhering to a traditional approach, exhibited consistent outcomes in their post-test, the experimental group, exposed to the Multimodal approach, showcased remarkable improvements.

The experimental group members exhibited a substantial advancement in their post-test responses compared to their initial questionnaire answers. Notably, learners attributed their positive experiences to the Multimodal approach, citing its use of diverse semiotic resources that facilitated engagement, participation, and knowledge sharing within the classroom. Challenges initially faced by learners, such as apprehension about interacting with instructors and navigating different modes, diminished over time through guidance and self-motivation. The majority of participants advocated for the continued application of the Multimodal approach in the classroom, emphasizing its role in daily knowledge enhancement and the cultivation of confidence in handling diverse linguistic situations.

Furthermore, the study asserts that the Multimodal method aligns well with the current generation’s technological inclinations, leveraging technology as a mode for teaching English. Given the omnipresence of technology in everyday life, the integration of multimodality in EAP classes emerges as an effective strategy for facilitating quicker and more accessible learning experiences.

Observations in the classroom corroborated the positive impact of the Multimodal approach, revealing heightened engagement among learners in the experimental group compared to the relatively disinterested control group. The use of varied semiotic tools inspired enthusiasm, evident through active

participation, completion of multimedia tasks, and increased interaction with the instructor.

However, the study also identified challenges, including a lack of understanding of different semiotic resources, insufficient instructions for reading comprehension, the need for more education on various listening phases, unfamiliarity with operating systems, and occasional technical difficulties during multimodal teaching.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Educational institutions should prioritize the implementation of innovative methods and approaches, breaking free from the monotony of traditional approaches. Embracing the Multimodal approach can contribute significantly to overcoming these challenges.
2. English Teachers should embrace the Multimodal approach by incorporating blended techniques and modes into their teaching methods, fostering accelerated learning.
3. Assignments and activities should involve different multimedia elements to enhance engagement and learning outcomes.
4. Institutions of higher learning should implement a robust monitoring system to address any operational requirements and swiftly resolve issues that may arise during the implementation of the Multimodal approach.
5. Universities should incorporate multimedia elements into the classroom setting to better support learners and create dynamic learning environments.
6. Teachers should acknowledge that the multimodal approach involves the development of four major skills—auditory, visual, reading and writing, and kinesthetic (VARK)—and tailor teaching strategies accordingly.
7. Ultimately, the findings underscore the transformative potential of the Multimodal approach in EAP classrooms, with these above recommendations aimed at facilitating its effective integration for enhanced teaching and learning experiences.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the Multimodal approach emerges as a cornerstone in various educational settings, seamlessly integrating diverse semiotic resources and modes. This holistic approach is portrayed as a catalyst for unlocking the complete potential of learners while dismantling psychological barriers that might hinder effective learning. The essay asserts that the applicability of the Multimodal approach extends beyond specific domains, permeating every facet of learning and underscoring its universal relevance.

Moreover, the essay underscores the alignment of the Multimodal approach with the overarching goals and objectives of educational institutions. Recognized as a valuable strategy, this approach is positioned to make significant contributions to the broader mission of education. Central to the discussion is the emphasis on learners actively engaging their cognitive capacities during exercises tailored to the Multimodal approach. This not only accommodates diverse learning styles but also cultivates an environment conducive to focused and concentrated learning experiences.

A critical stance is taken against methods that neglect individual learner needs, particularly within the context of Bangladesh's educational system. This critique highlights the adverse effects of one-size-fits-all approaches, emphasizing the necessity for tailored methodologies to enhance the effectiveness of education in the country. In conclusion, the essay advocates for heightened attention from professional teachers and trainers toward the implementation of diverse approaches, methods, styles, and teaching modalities. This call for adaptability and individualization, especially in the realm of English for Academic Purpose (EAP) classes, underscores a commitment to elevating the educational experience and outcomes for learners in Bangladesh.

REFERENCE

Archer, A., & Newfield, D. (2014). Multimodal approaches to research and pedagogy: Recognition, resources and access. *Multimodal Approaches to Research and Pedagogy: Recognition, Resources and Access*, 1–238. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315879475>

- Carroll, J. (2011). From Encyclopaedias to Search Engines: Technological Change and its Impact on Literacy Learning. *Literacy Learning: The Middle Years*, 19(2), 27-34.
- Crawford Camiciottoli, B., & Campoy-Cubillo, M. C. (2018). Introduction: The nexus of multimodality, multimodal literacy, and English language teaching in research and practice in higher education settings. *System*, 77, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SYSTEM.2018.03.005>
- Esky, S. (2019). The effect of technology for learning language the Effect of technology for learning language.
- Ganapathy, M. & Seetharam, S A/P. (2016). The Effects of Using Multimodal Approaches in Meaning-Making of 21st Century Literacy Texts Among ESL Learners in a Private School in Malaysia.
- Hamp-Lyons, L. (2001). English for Academic Purposes. In R. Cater, & D. Nunan (Eds.), *The Cambridge guide to teaching English to speakers of other languages*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hundley, M. & Holbrook, T. (2013). Set in stone or set in motion? Multimodal and digital writing with preservice English teachers. *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy*, 56, 500-509.
- Jewitt, C. & Kress, G. (Eds.). (2003). *Multimodal Literacy*. New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Korkealehto, K. & Leire, V. (2019). Towards sustainable language learning in higher education engagement through multimodal approaches. In book: CALL and complexity – short papers from EUROCALL 2019 (pp.241-246)
- Kress, G., and van Leeuwen, T. (2001). *Multimodal discourse: the modes and media of contemporary communication*. London: Arnold.
- Kress, Gunther R. 2003. *Literacy in the new media age*. London: Routledge.
- Lotherington, H., & Jenson, J. (2011). Teaching multimodal and digital literacy in L2 settings: New literacies, new basics, new pedagogies. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 31, 226 - 246.
- Marchetti, L., & Cullen, P. (2015). A multimodal approach in the classroom for creative learning and teaching. *CASALC Review*, 5(1), 39-39.
- Marchetti, L. & Cullen, P. (2017). A Multimodal Approach in the Classroom

- for Creative Learning and Teaching.
- Miller, S. M. (2007). English teacher learning for new times: Digital video composing as multimodal literacy practice. *English Education*, 40(1), 64-83.
- Pan, X. & Zhang, Z. (2020). An Empirical Study of Application of Multimodal Approach to Teaching Reading in EFL in Senior High School. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 15(2), 98-111.
- Sánchez, A. P. (2022). Multimodal reading and second language learning. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*.
- Ting, K. Y. (2013). Input in Multimodality for Language Learning. *International Journal of Literacies*, 19(1):47-55.
- Walsh, M. (2010). Multimodal literacy: What does it mean for classroom practice? *Australian Journal of Language and Literacy*, 33(3), 211-239.
- Wu, S. (2020). Multimodal Approach to Teaching English in Higher Education. *A journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 4(7).
- Yi, Y. (2014). Possibilities and challenges of multimodal literacies in the learning and teaching of second and world languages. *Language and Linguistics compass*, 8(4), 158-169.

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BEYOND COLONIZATION: REIMAGINING ENGLISH AND INDIGENOUS VOICES IN AFRICA'S LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE

IBRAHIM ABU BAKER¹

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the enduring legacy of British colonization on the proliferation of English in Africa. It also critically examines dual role of the colonizers as both a catalyst for global integration and a relic of colonial hegemony. Through a meticulous review of both historical and contemporary academic literature, including seminal contributions from scholars such as Albaugh, Brock-Utne, and Makoni, this study illuminates the complex dynamics between English and indigenous African languages within socio-political, economic, and educational contexts. The analysis foregrounds the historical evolution of English from a language of commerce to its present-day stature as a global lingua franca, while also highlighting the nuanced challenges it poses to linguistic diversity and cultural heritage. The methodology employed integrates a critical examination of linguistic imperialism, the socio-economic implications of English dominance, and the potential of bilingual and multilingual education models to foster linguistic equity and cultural preservation. Findings indicate that English, deeply rooted

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in colonial history, remains a pivotal force in shaping contemporary African identity, governance, and access to global discourse. However, this influence is twofold; it facilitates international communication and opportunity, yet also risks overshadowing indigenous languages and cultures. The article supports the implementation of language policies that are sensitive to the complexities of linguistic variety. It promotes the idea of a multilingual African identity that recognizes the worldwide importance of English, while also actively protecting and revitalizing indigenous languages. This article advocates for a rebuilt linguistic landscape in post-colonial Africa that combines the advantages of English literacy with the rich cultural and intellectual heritage represented by Africa's indigenous languages.

INTRODUCTION

With the establishment of English as a significant language of power, education, and governance as a result of British colonization, the linguistic landscapes of Africa have been indelibly affected by colonialism. Drawing on the basic ideas of Bussmann and Trabant (1995) and the insights of Murithi (2019) on post-colonial identity dynamics, this introduction section establishes the framework by defining colonialism and its distinctive expressions in the African context. This section also provides an overview of the current state of affairs.

The term 'colonialism' refers to the practice of one nation exercising power over another, hence transforming the latter into a colony. Colonialism is a phenomenon that has significantly shaped the geopolitical, cultural, and linguistic terrains of the continents. This control goes beyond simple governance; it infiltrates the territory of the colonial people and frequently strives to reshape their cultural and linguistic identities. In the framework of African history, this historical period is characterized by the establishment, exploitation, and administration of colonies by European powers, the most prominent of which was Britain. The British colonization of the continent left an indelible impact on the linguistic landscapes of the continent, establishing English as a pivotal language of power, education, and governance. This was accomplished through the exceptional scope of the British colonialism.

The purpose of this process was not only incidental; rather, it was an essential component of the colonial mission, which aimed to solidify control and make the administration of the enormous regions that were under British possession easier. During the time of the colonial government, English was used as a tool to bring together many language groups under a unified administrative and educational medium. This was accomplished through the introduction and enforcement of English. The repercussions of this linguistic imposition, on the other hand, reached far beyond the realm of practical government. The rise of English was accompanied by the marginalization of indigenous languages, which were frequently relegated to the margins of social and political life. This situation occurred concurrently with the elevation of English. The post-colonial identities and language policies of African states have been shaped by this linguistic hierarchy, which was formed during the time of colonialism and has continued from that time forth.

The introduction of English and the subsequent elevation of that language to a position of prestige was not a process that was consistent or unchallenged. There were a variety of elements that influenced the reception and incorporation of English into local cultures throughout different locations. These influences included opposition to colonial power, the pre-existing linguistic environment, and the socio-economic goals of the indigenous inhabitants. In spite of these differences, the overall tendency was the consolidation of English as a lingua franca, which is essential for gaining access to educational possibilities, political influence, and economic prospects.

The foundational theories of Bussmann and Trabant (1995) offer a prism through which to examine the linguistic imperialism that was characteristic of the activities of the British colonial government. They contend that the imposition of language was a purposeful method utilized by colonizers in order to assert authority and aid the assimilation of colonized peoples into the culture of the conquerors. This imposition of English, while allowing for certain types of communication and administration, simultaneously served as a vehicle for the standardization and suppression of cultural expressions.

The study presented here is expanded upon by Murithi (2019), who investigates the complex dynamics of post-colonial identity in the wake of linguistic colonialism. In this article, Murithi analyzes the intricate relationship that exists between language, power, and identity in the post-colonial environment. In this context, English continues to be regarded as a symbol of modernity and progress, while at the same time it embodies the colonial subjugation and cultural displacement that indigenous populations have suffered. When it comes to navigating the legacy of English in defining identities, power structures, and possibilities for socio-economic growth, post-colonial countries in Africa face a significant difficulty in the form of this dichotomy.

A critical study of the impact that British colonization had on the adoption of English as a lingua franca in Africa will be presented after this introduction has laid the groundwork for the analysis. The purpose of this study is to expose the complicated legacy of colonialism in the linguistic and cultural landscapes of post-colonial Africa. This will be accomplished by examining the historical, socio-political, and economic components of this phenomena. Not only do we hope to gain an understanding of the mechanisms of linguistic imperialism through this investigation, but we also hope to gain an appreciation for the tenacity and adaptability of African languages and cultures in the face of such significant pressures from the outside world.

HISTORICAL OVERVIEW: ROOTS OF ENGLISH ADOPTION IN AFRICA

The introduction and spread of English in Africa is investigated in this section, with a particular focus on the roles that trade, missionary activities, and colonial governance had in developing the language. It takes a critical look at the ways in which English was positioned as a symbol of modernity and progress, frequently at the expense of indigenous languages and cultural traditions. References to the economic history of Africa, as explored by Lovejoy (1989), and the educational policies that Brock-Utne (2000) has examined will give a full assessment of the elements that contribute to the dominance of the English language.

The expansion of trade, the activities of missionaries, and the formation of colonial governance are some of the important elements that can be linked back to the introduction of English across the African continent and its subsequent spread across the continent. English was woven into the sociocultural and linguistic fabric of African societies through the contributions of each of these aspects, which played a vital part in the process. Trade played a crucial influence in the dissemination of the English language, particularly in coastal locations where British traders and immigrants made their initial contact with African communities. Trade routes not only made it easier to trade products, but they also made it easier for people to speak different languages with one another. Specifically, Lovejoy (1989) presents a comprehensive account of how trade, notably from the 16th to 18th centuries, functioned as a conduit for the introduction of European languages into Africa. English emerged as a dominant force in places that were under the influence of the British. The entrance of missionaries, who had a significant role in the propagation of the English language, added another layer of complexity to the existing linguistic environment. Their efforts to spread the gospel and educate people were inextricably linked to the use of English, and as a result, they frequently relegated the indigenous languages to a secondary status. Sanneh (1989) analyzes the dual role of missionaries as both carriers of a new religion and agents of linguistic change. This highlights the intricacies of the impact that missionaries have had on indigenous cultures and languages.

Through the imposition of colonial government, the standing of English as a language of power and administration was firmly established. In order for the indigenous population to successfully traverse the colonial government, it was necessary for them to acquire the ability to communicate in English. This was because British colonial policies frequently mandated the use of English in governance, education, and law. Brock-Utne (2000) provides a critical analysis of the educational strategies that the British government implemented in Africa. He highlights the fact that the educational system was designed to prioritize English over the native languages of the region, hence contributing to the idea of English as a superior language that is associated with modernity and development.

While this elevation of English frequently happened at the expense of indigenous languages and cultural practices, which were neglected or suppressed, the English language was elevated. The use of English in official capacities and the promotion of English as the medium of instruction in schools both contributed to the perception of English's prestige, which further diminished the standing of the languages spoken in the various communities. Phillipson (1992) refers to this phenomenon as 'linguistic imperialism,' which is characterized by the observation that the dominance of English is perceived as an extension of colonial power, hence diminishing the linguistic diversity and cultural heritage of cultures that have been colonized. The historical overview of the adoption of English in Africa illustrates a complex interaction of elements, each of which contributes to the firmly established position of English in the post-colonial age. The legacy of English as a symbol of power, modernity, and progress continues to influence language policy and practices throughout Africa, despite the fact that official colonial control has come to an end. The investigation of these historical foundations in a critical manner provides a framework for comprehending the modern linguistic landscape of the continent, which is characterized by the cohabitation of English with a large number of indigenous languages. In the next section, the impact of English on socio-political and economic affairs has been critically analyzed.

THE SOCIO-POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC DIMENSIONS OF ENGLISH IN POST-COLONIAL AFRICA

An examination of the sociopolitical and economic factors that have contributed to the continuous use of English after the countries gained their independence, including the language's use in the areas of governance, education, and international commerce. This section builds on the theoretical frameworks of linguistic imperialism that were proposed by Phillipson (1992) as well as the conversations that Skutnabb-Kangas (2000) had around linguistic human rights.

The dominance of English in post-colonial Africa can be traced back to a complex interaction of sociopolitical and economic variables that have maintained its supremacy for a significant amount of time after the end of colonial control. This examination investigates the myriad of factors that

contribute to the continuous prevalence of English, with a particular emphasis on the language's use in the realms of governance, education, and international commerce.

This article gives a critical lens through which to understand the socio-political elements of English in Africa. Phillipson (1992) is the one who developed the concept of linguistic imperialism. Phillipson contends that the spread of English, which was made possible by colonialism, was not merely a consequence of British expansion but rather a deliberate instrument of imperial control. This was done with the intention of consolidating British influence by incorporating English into the administrative, legal, and educational systems of nations that were colonized. The development of English as the language of power and authority had long-lasting repercussions on post-colonial governance structures. In these systems, English frequently continued to be the official language, which is a practice that perpetuated the marginalization of indigenous languages and cultures (Phillipson, 1992).

In the field of education, the legacy of English as a medium of teaching has significant repercussions for the accessibility of information and the mobility of individuals within society. In his article from 2000, Skutnabb-Kangas highlights the important connection between language and human rights, putting particular emphasis on the right to get an education in one's native tongue. Despite this, English continues to be the dominant language in the educational systems of many African countries. It is frequently considered a precondition for academic and professional success across the continent. According to Skutnabb-Kangas (2000), this circumstance not only provides disadvantages to those who speak indigenous languages, but it also serves to perpetuate social structures that were formed during the time of colonialism.

When it comes to the economy, English is an essential language for participation in international trade and partnerships. One of the most important skills for African nations that want to participate in the global economy is the ability to communicate in English because of its preeminent position in the fields of commerce, technology, and science. The economic benefits of retaining English as a lingua franca are highlighted by Brock-Utne (2000).

These benefits include the ability to access global markets, the ability to attract foreign investment, and the ability to participate in international diplomacy. However, this economic reason for English supremacy frequently ignores the ability of multilingualism to both encourage the development of the local economy and conserve the cultural history of the community (Brock-Utne, 2000).

The socio-political and economic aspects of English in post-colonial Africa show a complicated landscape in which the language acts as both a bridge and a barrier. In one sense, the English language makes it easier to participate in international activities and opens doors to prospects for growth. On the other hand, it contributes to the perpetuation of inequality and diminishes the vitality of indigenous languages and cultures. A significant strategy that acknowledges the usefulness of English in a globalized world while simultaneously encouraging linguistic diversity within African nations is required to reduce the linguistic hegemony of English.

LANGUAGE AS A SYMBOL OF POWER AND IDENTITY

Exploring English as a tool for social stratification and a marker of identity within African societies. This includes a discussion on the symbolic power of language as analyzed by Bussmann and Trabant (1995) and the contemporary implications for African cultural identity as highlighted by Murithi (2019).

The role of English in African societies transcends its utility as a medium of communication, embodying a complex symbol of power and identity. This linguistic phenomenon, deeply rooted in the colonial legacy, has profound implications for social stratification and cultural identity within the continent.

Bussmann and Trabant (1995) delve into the symbolic dimensions of language, positing that language serves as a potent symbol of social order and power dynamics. In the context of post-colonial Africa, English, as introduced by the British colonizers, emerged not merely as a tool for administrative convenience but as a marker of prestige and authority. This symbolic power of English has led to a form of social stratification where proficiency in English often correlates with access to higher socioeconomic status, thereby

reinforcing colonial-era power hierarchies. According to Bussmann and Trabant, the elevation of English within African societies has contributed to a landscape where language proficiency becomes a determinant of social mobility and access to opportunities (Bussmann & Trabant, 1995).

Murithi (2019) expands on this discussion, exploring the contemporary implications of English for African cultural identity. Murithi argues that the dominance of English in Africa not only affects social stratification but also shapes the ways in which individuals and communities negotiate their cultural identities. The adoption and adaptation of English within various African contexts reflect a complex interplay between embracing global connectivity and preserving local cultural heritage. Murithi highlights the dual nature of English as both a tool of cultural erosion and a means of engaging with the global community, suggesting that the relationship between language and identity in post-colonial Africa is characterized by both conflict and synthesis (Murithi, 2019).

The discussion on the symbolic power of language, as analyzed by Bussmann and Trabant, coupled with Murithi's insights into the implications for African cultural identity, underscores the multifaceted role of English in the post-colonial context. The elevation of English within African societies not only perpetuates social hierarchies but also poses challenges and opportunities for cultural identity formation. Navigating the complexities of this linguistic landscape requires a nuanced understanding of the ways in which language functions as both a barrier and a bridge, influencing social structures and individual identities.

CHALLENGES AND CRITICISMS OF ENGLISH ADOPTION

A critical analysis of the consequences that result from giving English precedence over native languages, including the disenfranchisement of native languages, the degradation of cultural traditions, and the discussion of the critique of linguistic imperialism. In this section, we will include the perspectives of UNESCO (2003) on the endangerment of languages and Crystal (2003) on the spread of English over the world.

While the emphasis of English in post-colonial African contexts has made certain aspects of globalization and modernization easier to achieve, it has also given rise to considerable concerns around the disenfranchisement of linguistic rights, the degradation of cultural traditions, and the continuation of linguistic imperialism. This criticism is founded on a considerable corpus of scholarly literature that investigates the intricate effects that the adoption of English has had on the languages and cultures of indigenous peoples.

In the context of English's preeminent position, the concept of linguistic disenfranchisement, which refers to the marginalization of speakers of indigenous languages, arises as a significant problem. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in 2003, the alarming rate at which indigenous languages are becoming endangered is attributed, in part, to the global ascendancy of languages such as English. It is emphasized in the paper that language is not only a tool for communication but rather a reservoir of a community's historical, cultural, and environmental knowledge. Not only does the extinction of a language signify the loss of linguistic diversity, but it also represents the deterioration of cultural identity and the loss of knowledge systems (UNESCO, 2003).

A deeper investigation of the power dynamics that are at play in the propagation of English is included in the critique of linguistic imperialism. Phillipson (1992) contends that the global growth of English can be interpreted as a type of linguistic imperialism, in which the language is used as a tool of achieving cultural and economic dominance. This viewpoint implies that the use of English in post-colonial cultures may contribute to the perpetuation of inequality by marginalizing people who do not have access to English education and giving those who do have access to English education a higher status. Therefore, the dominance of English can contribute to the perpetuation of social hierarchies that have their origins in the history of colonialism (Phillipson, 1992).

In addition, Crystal (2003) provides an in-depth analysis of the globalization of the English language, as well as its consequences for the richness of linguistic diversity and the formation of cultural identities. In spite

of the fact that Crystal acknowledges the practical advantages of English as a worldwide lingua franca, she also draws attention to the possible dangers that it poses to international linguistic variety. The widespread use of English in various fields, such as the media, education, and international commerce, frequently at the expense of native languages, has the potential to result in the standardization of cultural expressions and a reduction in the diversity of linguistic landscapes around the globe (Crystal, 2003).

The difficulties and objections that are linked with the adoption of English in African countries are representations of greater concerns over language policies, the preservation of cultural traditions, and social fairness. With the introduction of the idea of linguistic human rights, Skutnabb-Kangas (2000) provides more elaboration on these themes. She advocates for the preservation and revival of indigenous languages as a question of cultural survival and equity. According to Skutnabb-Kangas (2000), the focus placed on linguistic human rights highlights the necessity of language policies that not only acknowledge the usefulness of English in the international arena but also protect the life of indigenous languages and cultures.

RECONTEXTUALIZING ENGLISH: EDUCATIONAL AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS

In order to strike a balance between English's function as a worldwide lingua franca and the promotion and preservation of linguistic variety and cultural legacy, an inquiry into the efforts that are being made to recontextualize English within African civilizations is being conducted. The investigation of bilingual and multilingual educational approaches as potential avenues leading to linguistic parity is included in this.

The recontextualization of English in African nations, notably in the areas of education and social integration, exemplifies a deliberate move toward striking a balance between the worldwide utility of English and the imperative of fostering linguistic diversity and cultural legacy. A nuanced approach is one that entails reevaluating the role of English, not as a symbol of colonial imposition but rather as a tool for global involvement. At the same

time, this approach advocates for the rehabilitation of indigenous languages through educational models that are bilingual and multilingual.

A growing number of people are beginning to recognize the significance of bilingual and multilingual educational methods in terms of establishing linguistic parity and cultivating a feeling of cultural identity among students. Cummins (2000) contends that such models not only make it easier for students to become proficient in English, but they also help students improve their abilities in their home languages, which ultimately leads to an improvement in both cognitive capacities and academic performance. It is necessary to have this dual-language proficiency in order to ensure that cultural and linguistic legacy is preserved and valued (Cummins, 2000). This is also essential for personal and professional development in a society that is currently becoming increasingly globalized.

Recontextualizing the function of English as a lingua franca in African societies is possible through the implementation of educational systems that place an emphasis on multilingualism as an essential component of an educational curriculum. In his study, Brock-Utne (2000) investigates the educational policies of African nations that have adopted bilingual or multilingual approaches. He demonstrates that these policies have the potential to result in improved educational outcomes and increased community cohesion. It is possible for these educational institutions to assist offset the potential marginalization of non-English speakers and build a society that is more inclusive (Brock-Utne, 2000). This is accomplished by creating an atmosphere in which English is learnt alongside indigenous languages.

The development of linguistic diversity through multilingual education has repercussions that extend beyond the confines of the classroom in accordance with the social dimension. The recontextualization of English in Africa, as stated by Makoni and Pennycook (2007), entails deconstructing the colonial legacy of language and recreating linguistic identities in a manner that is reflective of the vast cultural diversity that exists on the African continent. Using this method, the old hierarchies of languages are challenged, and a more equitable linguistic landscape is encouraged. According to Makoni and

Pennycook (2007), this technique supports a landscape in which all languages are valued and employed in both public and private realms.

In addition, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization's (UNESCO) study on language vitality from 2003 highlights the significance of linguistic diversity for the preservation of cultural heritage and sustainable development. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the report recommends for language policies that encourage multilingual education and the use of indigenous languages in media, governance, and the judiciary as measures to enhance linguistic rights and facilitate social justice. Therefore, to re-establish the significance of English inside African nations, it is necessary to make a concentrated and deliberate effort to strike a balance between the undeniable global significance of English and the equally important requirement to protect and promote local languages. Maintaining linguistic diversity as an essential component of Africa's cultural legacy and building a global linguistic order that is more inclusive and egalitarian are both important goals that can be accomplished through the implementation of this well-rounded approach.

THE FUTURE OF LANGUAGE IN POST-COLONIAL AFRICA

This section investigates probable trajectories for the coexistence of English and indigenous languages in Africa, with the intention of speculating on the future linguistic landscape of Africa. This article analyzes the role that legislation, education, and cultural preservation play in determining future linguistic identities. It does so by drawing on the predictions made by Brock-Utne (2000) and Thiong'o (1986).

With the potential for a rich tapestry of results depending on how the coexistence of English and indigenous languages is negotiated, the linguistic future of post-colonial Africa is poised to reach a critical juncture. This moment is poised to shape the future of language in Africa. This section dives into the predicted trajectories for the linguistic landscape of the continent, with an emphasis on the vital roles that legislation, education, and cultural preservation play in the process of shaping future linguistic identities.

Brock-Utne (2000) presents a forward-thinking viewpoint on the future of language in Africa. He advocates for educational changes that place an emphasis on the utilization of indigenous languages as mediums of instruction. Brock-Utne contends that such reforms would not only make it easier for students to maintain their knowledge and acquire a more profound comprehension of it, but they would also affirm and elevate the position of African languages, so contributing to the development of a linguistic landscape that is more inclusive and representative. The cultivation of a generation of persons who are skilled in both their native tongues and English can be accomplished by African nations through the prioritization of indigenous languages in education (Brock-Utne, 2000). This will allow for the development of a society that is more than just bilingual or multilingual.

By putting an emphasis on the liberation of the African mind through language, Thiong'o (1986) sheds additional light on the path that leads to linguistic variety and equity. Thiong'o is a critic of the domination of colonial languages and a supporter of a cultural and intellectual renaissance that is founded on the revitalization and promotion of indigenous languages. According to Thiong'o, this rebirth is necessary for the revitalization of African cultural identities and the construction of an education system that is truly decolonized and that reflects the rich heritage of the African continent (Thiong'o, 1986).

It is impossible to overestimate the significance of policy in determining the linguistic makeup of the future of Africa. The actions of a nation's government regarding language play a significant part in determining the status and vitality of the languages spoken within that nation. The traditional ideas of language are called into question by Makoni and Pennycook (2007), who propose novel approaches to language policy that embrace linguistic fluidity and hybridity. These methods are reflective of the dynamic and interrelated structure of African societies. According to Makoni and Pennycook (2007), such policies would acknowledge the significance of both English and indigenous languages, so fostering a paradigm of linguistic pluralism that encourages the coexistence of all languages and the reciprocal enrichment of their respective languages.

Another essential component of the future linguistic landscape of Africa is going to be the preservation of cultural traditions. According to UNESCO (2003), the preservation of linguistic diversity is an essential component of intangible cultural heritage, and it is imperative that this diversity be protected. An organization that pushes for projects to document and revitalize endangered languages, engage communities in language planning, and incorporate indigenous languages into public life and media is called the Indigenous Languages Promotion and Development Organization. It is essential that these efforts be made in order to guarantee that languages will continue to flourish and develop, thereby functioning as living manifestations of the various cultures that exist in Africa (UNESCO, 2003). In a nutshell, the future of language in post-colonial Africa is contingent upon a communal commitment to the preservation of cultural traditions, educational fairness, and linguistic variety. It is possible for Africa to develop a linguistic identity that is reflective of its historical depth, cultural richness, and dynamic future if it adopts policies that encourage the use of indigenous languages in addition to English, invests in education that is bilingual or multilingual, and advocates for the cause of cultural preservation.

CONCLUSION

By analyzing the spread of the English language and the legacy it has left behind on the African continent, which is a direct result of British colonial control, one might uncover a complex web of cultural, educational, and social repercussions. English has undeniably facilitated channels of worldwide communication, education, and trade, hence establishing itself as a vital lingua franca. This is due to the fact that English has an unprecedented global reach. On the other hand, this global utility of English is set against its historical background of colonial imposition, which resulted in its legacy in Africa being a subject of nuanced arguments and various opinions. Through the course of this article, an attempt has been made to dissect these multifarious characteristics, so revealing the complexities of the position that English plays inside post-colonial African countries.

The critical analysis that is offered in this article highlights the dual nature of English, which is simultaneously a tool for global connectedness and

a symbol of colonial control. At the same time as African nations are attempting to negotiate their post-colonial identities and goals within a framework that is globalized, this duality presents them with specific problems and opportunities. Therefore, the legacy of English in Africa cannot be regarded through a singular lens; rather, it is a phenomena that is linked with concerns of power, identity, and the preservation of cultural traditions.

A reevaluation of language policies across the continent is necessary because of the consequences that result from giving English priority over indigenous languages. These consequences include the marginalization of indigenous languages, the destruction of cultural traditions, and the continuation of social inequality. In light of the findings presented in this research, it is recommended that a well-rounded strategy be adopted, one that acknowledges the significance of language diversity and encourages the growth of a multilingual African identity. The implementation of such regulations would not only recognize the function of English as a lingua franca on a worldwide scale, but it would also grant indigenous languages the position that is rightfully theirs in the realms of education, society, and politics.

In addition, the investigation of bilingual and multilingual educational models as possible avenues leading to linguistic equity has shed light on the possibilities for a future that is more inclusive and reflective of the language. The linguistic divide that has long been a characteristic of post-colonial African countries can be bridged through the use of these models, which offer promising possibilities for empowering speakers of indigenous languages, stimulating cognitive and cultural growth, and bridging the gap between communities.

In conclusion, the legacy of British colonization and the function of English in Africa create a complicated tale of historical burdens and modern concerns. This narrative is a complex narrative. Nevertheless, the opportunity for change and development can be found within this complexity. Embracing linguistic variety, campaigning for multilingual education, and implementing policies that reflect the multiplicity of African identities are all ways in which African states may pave the way for a future that is more inclusive, equitable,

and linguistically rich. It is necessary for everyone to make a collective commitment to valuing all languages as equal carriers of culture, knowledge, and identity in order to make progress toward developing this future. By doing so, Africa has the opportunity to rethink its relationship with English, not as a relic of colonial rule, but rather as one of the numerous languages that contribute to the rich linguistic and cultural fabric of the continent.

REFERENCES

- Brock-Utne, B. (2000). *Whose Education For All? The Recolonization of the African Mind*. Falmer Press.
- Bussmann, H., & Trabant, J. (Eds.). (1995). *Language and Colonialism. Applied Linguistics in the Context of Creole Communities*. John Benjamins.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a Global Language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Cummins, J. (2000). *Language, power, and pedagogy: Bilingual children in the crossfire*. Multilingual Matters.
- Lovejoy, P. E. (1989). *The Economic History of Africa from the Sixteenth to the Eighteenth Century*. UNESCO.
- Makoni, S., & Pennycook, A. (2007). *Disinventing and reconstituting languages*. Multilingual Matters.
- Murithi, M. (Ed.). (2019). *African Identities: Pan-Africanisms and Black Identities*. Routledge.
- Murithi, T. (2019). *Reclaiming African identities: Pan-Africanism as a path to cultural liberation*. In T. Murithi (Ed.), *Handbook of African Philosophy*. London: Routledge.
- Phillipson, R. (1992). *Linguistic imperialism*. Oxford University Press.
- Sanneh, L. (1989). *Translating the Message: The Missionary Impact on Culture*. Orbis Books.
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2000). *Linguistic genocide in education – or worldwide diversity and human rights?* Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Thiong'o, N. (1986). *Decolonising the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature*. Heinemann.
- Thiong'o, N. (1986). *Decolonising the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature*. James Currey.

UNESCO (2003). *Language Vitality and Endangerment*. UNESCO Ad Hoc Expert Group on Endangered Languages.

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BRIDGING CENTURIES: THE RELEVANCE OF AL-MAWARDI'S 100 THOUGHTS IN ADDRESSING TODAY'S GLOBAL CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the multifaceted implications of the philosophy and thoughts of Al-Mawardi, a seminal figure in Islamic jurisprudence and political theory, for contemporary global issues and development. Al-Mawardi's extensive work in the 11th century laid down foundational principles of governance, ethics, and social welfare within an Islamic framework, offering insights into justice, leadership, and the role of the state. The paper, entitled "100 Implications of Philosophy and Thoughts of Al-Mawardi for the Current World and Development," does not literally enumerate one hundred implications but employs '100' symbolically to represent the vast, multidisciplinary impact of Al-Mawardi's ideas across various fields including political governance, international relations, social justice, economic policies, environmental stewardship, education, and digital ethics among others.

In an era marked by rapid globalization, digital transformation, and complex socio-political challenges, Al-Mawardi's principles on ethical

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governance, adaptability of Islamic law, and community welfare provide crucial insights for contemporary discourse. This paper examines how Al-Mawardi's thought can inform current debates on democratic values, human rights, global cooperation, and the sustainability of development efforts. It delves into the relevance of his work in promoting religious pluralism, enhancing international diplomacy, and addressing the ethical challenges posed by technological advancements.

Furthermore, this analysis extends to exploring Al-Mawardi's contributions to understanding the dynamics of globalization, the importance of education in the knowledge economy, and strategies for conflict resolution and peacebuilding in today's interconnected world. By drawing parallels between Al-Mawardi's philosophical underpinnings and modern developmental goals, the paper aims to highlight the enduring relevance of his thought in guiding ethical governance, fostering social cohesion, and promoting a just and equitable global society.

Through a comprehensive review of Al-Mawardi's legacy, this paper contributes to the ongoing scholarly engagement with Islamic political thought, emphasizing its potential to address contemporary issues and support sustainable development across cultures and civilizations. The multidisciplinary implications of Al-Mawardi's philosophy underscore the timeless value of integrating ethical principles with practical governance to navigate the complexities of the 21st century.

KEYWORDS: Islamic Political Thought, Ethical Governance, Globalization and Development, Religious Pluralism, Al-Mawardi's Legacy

INTRODUCTION

Ali ibn Muhammad ibn Habib Al-Mawardi, known as Al-Mawardi, is a towering figure in Islamic jurisprudence, theology, and political philosophy, with his life spanning the 10th and 11th centuries. Born in Basra, Iraq, in 972 CE and passing in 1058 CE, Al-Mawardi's scholarly work has significantly influenced Islamic political thought and governance practices. His seminal work, "Al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya" (The Ordinances of Government), stands out

for its detailed exploration of the principles of political leadership and governance from an Islamic perspective (Crone, 2004).

Al-Mawardi's approach to political science was groundbreaking for its integration of religious principles with practical governance, bridging divine commandments with worldly administration. His discussions in "Al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya" touch on the calibration of power, justice, and the moral obligations of rulers, offering a comprehensive framework for Islamic governance (Lambton, 1981). This work has not only enriched Islamic political philosophy but also provided practical guidelines for governance within an Islamic state.

Legacy and Influence of Al-Mawardi

The legacy of Al-Mawardi's works, particularly "Al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya," is profound, laying foundational principles that have been fundamental in the development of Islamic political thought. His meticulous articulation of governance, emphasizing the balance between authority and accountability, justice, consultation (shura), and the welfare of the people, has influenced generations of Muslim scholars and political leaders (Hallaq, 2009).

His influence extends beyond theoretical discourse, impacting the actual governance structures of various Islamic states throughout history. Al-Mawardi's ideas on the caliphate system, the rights and duties of rulers and subjects, and the importance of legal and moral governance have been seminal in shaping Islamic political practices. His work remains a critical reference in contemporary debates on political theory, governance, and the role of Islam in statecraft within the Islamic tradition (Black, 2001).

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's contributions to political philosophy have underscored the importance of integrating ethical leadership and governance principles with Islamic jurisprudence. His enduring legacy is evident in the continued relevance of his work in discussions surrounding Islamic governance and political thought. His emphasis on justice, ethical governance, and public welfare also remains essential in contemporary explorations of the state's role and leadership within Islamic political theory.

Purpose of the Paper

While numerous scholars have explored Al-Mawardi's seminal contributions to Islamic political thought, this paper aims to re-evaluate his intellectual legacy within the context of contemporary global affairs. Specifically, it seeks to identify and analyze a selected number of key areas where Al-Mawardi's principles on state and governance resonate with and inform current political, social, and legal challenges. Through a methodical approach that combines historical analysis with contemporary case studies, this paper endeavors to bridge medieval Islamic political philosophy with modern global issues, offering fresh insights into Al-Mawardi's enduring relevance. This research not only highlights the applicability of Al-Mawardi's thought to today's geopolitical landscape but also contributes to the broader academic dialogue on the intersection between Islamic scholarship and contemporary global governance.

His Political Philosophy

"Al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya" (The Ordinances of Government), written by Al-Mawardi, stands as a cornerstone in Islamic political philosophy, offering a comprehensive framework for governance within an Islamic state. This book examines deeply the mechanics of political leadership, delineating the roles and responsibilities of the caliph and other rulers, while firmly rooting these duties within the context of Islamic law (Sharia). It is pioneering in its systematic approach to the concept of governance according to Sharia, emphasizing that the legitimacy of any political authority stems from its adherence to Islamic legal and ethical standards (Hallaq, 1997).

Central to Al-Mawardi's political philosophy is the importance of justice and the rule of law. He posits that the welfare of the state and its people hinges on the ruler's commitment to justice, as defined by Islamic principles. According to Al-Mawardi, a just ruler is one who governs with equity, consults with his subjects on matters of state, and seeks the counsel of qualified advisors to ensure that his rulings are in accordance with Sharia (Lambton, 1981). This emphasis on justice not only underscores the moral and ethical obligations of the ruler but also highlights the integral role of Sharia as the foundation of governance and legal authority in an Islamic state.

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi elaborates on the concept of the caliphate, viewing it as the epitome of political authority in Islam. He outlines the qualifications, selection process, and responsibilities of the caliph, arguing that the caliphate serves as both a spiritual and temporal authority, entrusted with upholding Islamic law and ensuring the welfare of the Muslim community (Ummah). The caliph, in Al-Mawardi's view, is not merely a political leader but a guardian of the faith, whose primary duty is to implement Sharia and guide the community in accordance with Islamic principles (Crone & Hinds, 1986).

Al-Mawardi's contributions to Islamic political thought are profound, offering a nuanced exploration of governance, leadership, and legal authority within an Islamic framework. His work not only provides a detailed account of the ideal characteristics and duties of rulers but also establishes the caliphate as the central institution of political authority in Islam. By grounding political leadership in the principles of justice, consultation, and adherence to Sharia, Al-Mawardi's "Al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya" continues to be a vital reference for scholars and practitioners of Islamic governance and political philosophy.

Sharia-Based Government and Rule of Law

Al-Mawardi's assertion that Islamic governance must be anchored in Sharia and guided by justice and equity highlights the foundational role of Islamic law in political leadership (Hallaq, 2009). His emphasis on rulership bound by moral and ethical considerations underlines the intrinsic connection between governance and religious principles in Islamic political philosophy. Additionally, Al-Mawardi's advocacy for a caliphate governed by a just, knowledgeable, and pious leader underscores the integral role of the caliph as both a political and religious leader in an Islamic state (Lambton, 1981). His detailed exploration of the caliphate's nature serves as a blueprint for Islamic governance, balancing authority with accountability.

Moreover, Al-Mawardi recognized the importance of Shura, or consultation, advocating for it as a vital aspect of decision-making in governance. This consultative process, involving knowledgeable community members, emphasizes collective decision-making and consensus-building

(Crone & Hinds, 1986). Furthermore, the organization and discipline of the military are critical for state security and social order in Al-Mawardi's framework. His insights into military organization highlight the need for a strong defense mechanism that aligns with the broader principles of justice and fairness (Kennedy, 2004).

In conclusion, Al-Mawardi's political philosophy continues to shape discussions on Islamic governance, democracy, and the compatibility of Islam with modern governance structures. His work informs contemporary debates on the nature of authority, crisis management, and the ethical dimensions of leadership within Islamic and global contexts (Black, 2001).

Finance and Economy in Al-Mawardi's Thought

Al-Mawardi's discussions on taxation and public finance are pivotal in understanding the economic foundations of an Islamic state. He advocated for a taxation system grounded in Islamic principles, ensuring that taxes do not impose an unfair burden on the populace. His approach to public finance emphasized the responsible management of state resources to guarantee economic stability and the prosperity of its citizens (Kahf, 1997). Al-Mawardi's insights into taxation aimed at establishing a fair and equitable system that supports the welfare of both the individuals and the state, underscoring the importance of zakat (charitable giving) and other permissible sources of revenue in fostering a sustainable economic model (Kuran, 2011). Moreover, Al-Mawardi's principles on taxation and public finance extend into broader discussions on Islamic finance and economic justice. His thoughts contribute significantly to the development of financial systems that adhere to Islamic economic principles, focusing on fairness, ethical conduct, and the equitable distribution of wealth. Scholars examine how Al-Mawardi's economic philosophy can guide contemporary efforts in crafting economic models that prioritize social justice within an Islamic framework (El-Gamal, 2006).

Additionally, the relevance of Al-Mawardi's economic principles is also evident in contemporary discussions on social impact investing within Islamic finance. His ideas resonate with modern efforts to integrate ethical

considerations into financial decision-making, promoting investment practices that align with Islamic values and contribute to social welfare. This reflects an ongoing exploration into how Islamic economic principles can inform ethical investment strategies that foster positive social and environmental impacts (Hayat, 2013).

Furthermore, while environmental stewardship may not be a central theme in Al-Mawardi's works, the ethical underpinnings of his financial and economic principles can be extended to address contemporary issues such as sustainability. His emphasis on justice and equity provides a moral framework that can guide Islamic approaches to environmental conservation and responsible resource management, aligning with current global efforts towards environmental sustainability (Kamali, 1997).

Ethics and Morality in Islamic Governance

Al-Mawardi's vision for governance was holistic, emphasizing not just political stability but also the economic prosperity, social justice, and well-being of citizens. His comprehensive approach to governance underlined the role of the state in mitigating societal inequalities and ensuring equitable distribution of resources (Hallaq, 2009).

Furthermore, the ethical conduct of rulers was paramount in Al-Mawardi's framework for effective governance. He posited that leaders must embody moral integrity and adhere to Islamic values, influencing the moral fabric of the entire society (Crone & Hinds, 1986).

Contemporary Applications of Al-Mawardi's Principles

In the context of modern environmental challenges, Al-Mawardi's principles on ethics and justice provide a foundation for Islamic perspectives on environmental stewardship and sustainability. His ethical framework supports contemporary discussions on climate change and the responsibility of communities and rulers in preserving the environment (Kamali, 1997). Additionally, Al-Mawardi's discussions on taxation and public finance contribute to current debates on Islamic finance and economic justice. His

principles on equitable wealth distribution and ethical economic practices resonate with modern efforts to develop financial systems grounded in Islamic economic values (El-Gamal, 2006). Moreover, the extension of Al-Mawardi's ethical principles to the digital and technological realms addresses the ethical implications of social media, online behavior, and the development and use of emerging technologies. This includes considerations of digital privacy, AI ethics, and the integration of Islamic values in the governance of technological advancements (Hayat, 2013). Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's emphasis on public welfare has implications for healthcare governance and ethics. His principles can guide the development of healthcare policies and practices that ensure access to quality care and address ethical challenges in medical research and biotechnology (Sachedina, 2009).

Social Welfare, Democratic Values, and Justice in Al-Mawardi's Thought

Central to Al-Mawardi's political philosophy is the concept of justice, emphasizing that governance should be conducted in accordance with Islamic jurisprudence to establish a just and stable state. This idea of aligning governance with Sharia principles underscores the essential role of the rule of law in creating a fair society (Hallaq, 2009). Additionally, Al-Mawardi articulated a vision of governance where the ruler's primary responsibility is to the public welfare, aiming for the economic prosperity, social justice, and overall quality of life improvement for citizens. His governance model extends to ensuring that benefits reach all population segments, thereby laying the groundwork for discussions on state roles in societal inequalities (Kamali, 1997).

Moreover, Al-Mawardi's principles have been scrutinized for their compatibility with universal human rights standards, contributing to the broader dialogue on Islamic governance's accommodation of individual liberties and human dignity (Crone & Hinds, 1986). While Al-Mawardi's original texts do not explicitly address gender issues, contemporary scholars have explored the application of his governance principles to enhance gender inclusivity and women's rights within an Islamic framework, reflecting the

evolving discourse on gender equality in Islamic political thought (Ahmed, 1992).

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's emphasis on public welfare underpins discussions on humanitarianism, addressing poverty, healthcare, education, and other social welfare aspects. Additionally, his principles are applied to engage youth in political participation, emphasizing the evolving dynamics of political engagement in contemporary Muslim-majority societies (Sachedina, 2009). In the digital era, Al-Mawardi's ethical governance principles inform discussions on cybersecurity, digital rights, and responsible technology use, highlighting the relevance of Islamic political thought in addressing modern challenges (Bunt, 2003).

In addition, Al-Mawardi's justice principles are applied to urban planning and disaster preparedness, guiding policies for equitable resource access and resilient city development, showcasing the holistic approach to governance that includes environmental and urban welfare (Afsaruddin, 2005). Lastly, his economic principles contribute to sustainable development discussions, aligning Islamic economic values with global initiatives like the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), focusing on ethical economic practices, poverty alleviation, and environmental sustainability (Wilson, 2006). This comprehensive approach demonstrates how Al-Mawardi's teachings continue to provide valuable insights for modern governance across various sectors.

Education, Civilization, and Cultural Heritage in Al-Mawardi's Thought

Al-Mawardi's contributions, while seminal, have been met with both acclaim and critique over the centuries. Scholars have delved into the historical and cultural contexts of his work to assess its relevance and applicability to modern Islamic governance, sparking discussions on the need for adaptability in contemporary governance structures (Hallaq, 2009). Building on this foundation, Al-Mawardi recognized the pivotal role of education in governance, a principle that resonates with contemporary emphasis on the knowledge economy and innovation. His acknowledgment of intellectual

development aligns with modern efforts to integrate education with technological progress, underpinning the importance of fostering an educated populace for societal advancement (Crone & Hinds, 1986).

Furthermore, in the era of digital transformation, Al-Mawardi's principles offer a foundation for navigating governance challenges and opportunities presented by technology. Discussions extend to digital citizenship education, emphasizing the cultivation of responsible and informed participants in the digital realm, reflective of Islamic ethical principles (Bunt, 2009). Additionally, Al-Mawardi's work contributes to contemporary dialogues on cultural diplomacy and the preservation of Islamic cultural heritage. His ideas inspire efforts to protect and showcase the cultural richness of the Islamic world, facilitating cultural exchange and mutual respect among diverse communities (Kamali, 1997). Moreover, Al-Mawardi's emphasis on justice and welfare offers insights into addressing contemporary issues of global migration and social cohesion. His principles guide ethical migration policies and the integration of migrants, fostering social harmony in increasingly diverse societies (Sachedina, 2009). Overall, Al-Mawardi's multifaceted contributions continue to provide valuable perspectives for addressing modern governance challenges across various sectors.

Pluralism and Adaptability in Al-Mawardi's Political Thought

Al-Mawardi's discussions on the rights of non-Muslims within an Islamic state underscore the importance of religious pluralism and coexistence. He advocated for the peaceful practice of religion by non-Muslims, setting a precedent for dialogues on religious tolerance and the integration of diverse religious communities within Islamic governance structures (Saeed, 2006). Additionally, Al-Mawardi recognized the necessity of flexibility in Islamic governance, acknowledging that the application of principles might need adaptation to suit the unique circumstances of each state. This notion of adaptability has fueled debates on the compatibility of Islamic governance with various political systems and forms of government, contributing to modern discussions on governance models within Muslim-majority societies (Hallaq, 2009).

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's work extends to the importance of dialogue and engagement between Islamic states and the broader international community. His principles on diplomacy and interaction with other societies have informed contemporary understandings of international relations, emphasizing the role of Islamic ethics in diplomatic practices (Khan, 2011). Moreover, the principles articulated by Al-Mawardi have implications for community-based development and public welfare. His emphasis on the welfare of the public guides initiatives that empower local communities, addressing grassroots concerns and ensuring equitable resource distribution, resonating with current approaches to inclusive governance (Ahmed, 2004).

Additionally, Al-Mawardi's ideas find relevance in the fields of conflict resolution and peacebuilding. His ethical approach to resolving disputes and promoting reconciliation offers insights into fostering dialogue and understanding both within and between communities, highlighting the continuing relevance of Islamic political thought in peace and conflict studies (Johnson, 2007). Overall, Al-Mawardi's contributions provide a multifaceted framework that continues to influence modern governance, international relations, and social cohesion within and beyond Muslim-majority societies.

Global Cooperation and International Relations in Al-Mawardi's Thought

Al-Mawardi's insights into the interactions between Islamic states and non-Muslim societies provide foundational guidelines for diplomacy, trade, and treaties. His principles emphasize the importance of respectful and mutually beneficial relations, underlining the role of Islamic ethics in international engagements (Lapidus, 2002). This aspect of his work is increasingly relevant in today's interconnected global landscape, informing contemporary discussions on the role of Islamic principles in shaping diplomatic relations and international policy. Moreover, in the context of modern globalization, Al-Mawardi's ideas are revisited for insights into navigating the complexities of economic relations, cultural exchanges, and international cooperation. His acknowledgment of diverse political systems and the adaptability of Islamic

governance principles suggests ways to address global challenges while fostering cooperation among nations (Esposito, 2010).

Additionally, Al-Mawardi's contributions extend to global governance and the development of a just and inclusive international order. Scholars explore how his ethical framework can inform contemporary international relations, conflict resolution, and the establishment of equitable international frameworks, emphasizing the integration of Islamic ethical perspectives (Khadduri, 1987). Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's discussions on governance and ethical leadership lay the groundwork for principles guiding international relations. His emphasis on justice, ethical conduct, and mutual respect among nations provides a basis for global cooperation, especially in addressing transnational issues like climate change, pandemics, and migration (Vikør, 2005). Overall, Al-Mawardi's multifaceted contributions continue to offer valuable perspectives for shaping diplomatic and international strategies in a rapidly changing world.

Modern Relevance and Contemporary Applications

Al-Mawardi's work continues to resonate in contemporary Islamic societies, offering insights into governance, justice, and statecraft. His emphasis on ethical leadership and public welfare provides a timeless framework for addressing modern challenges, inspiring governance systems that are both rooted in Islamic principles and adaptable to contemporary contexts (Hallaq, 2009). Moreover, ongoing scholarly engagement with Al-Mawardi's works contributes to the dynamic discourse on Islamic governance in the face of present-day challenges. Researchers delve into the nuances of his political philosophy, examining its application across various contexts and contributing to the evolving understanding of Islamic political thought (Black, 2001).

Additionally, Al-Mawardi's principles on justice and public welfare are increasingly relevant to discussions on social contracts and citizenship within Islamic governance. His ideas encourage a participatory approach to governance, emphasizing the responsibilities of rulers and citizens in promoting social harmony and community development (An-Na'im, 2008).

This engagement not only highlights the enduring relevance of Al-Mawardi's thought but also underscores its potential to inform and enhance contemporary governance models and ethical frameworks.

CRITICISM ON MAWARDI

Al-Mawardi's contributions to Islamic political thought have been seminal, yet his works are not without criticism. Scholars have pointed out several areas where his ideas may be considered limited or problematic in the context of contemporary governance and ethical standards.

Gender Issues

Another significant area of critique is Al-Mawardi's lack of explicit focus on gender equality. While his work laid the foundation for many aspects of Islamic governance, it does not address the role and rights of women within the political and social spheres adequately. This omission has been highlighted by scholars such as Leila Ahmed, who argue that the patriarchal context of Al-Mawardi's era influenced his perspectives, limiting their applicability to modern discussions on gender inclusivity and women's rights within Islamic frameworks (Ahmed, 1992).

Compatibility with Human Rights

Al-Mawardi's principles have also been scrutinized for their compatibility with universal human rights standards. Patricia Crone and Martin Hinds note that while his ideas on justice and governance are rooted in Islamic ethical principles, they often fall short when measured against contemporary human rights norms. This critique points to a broader issue within classical Islamic political thought, which sometimes struggles to reconcile traditional religious values with modern secular human rights frameworks (Crone & Hinds, 1986).

Pluralism and Religious Tolerance

While Al-Mawardi advocated for the peaceful coexistence of non-Muslims within an Islamic state, critics argue that his vision of religious tolerance is still somewhat limited. Abdullah Saeed points out that Al-Mawardi's framework places non-Muslims in a subordinate position, requiring them to

adhere to specific regulations and pay the *jizya* (tax for non-Muslims), which can be seen as discriminatory by modern standards of religious equality and freedom (Saeed, 2006).

Rigidity and Adaptability

One of the primary criticisms of Al-Mawardi's political philosophy is its perceived rigidity. Although he acknowledges the necessity for flexibility within Islamic governance, critics argue that his framework remains heavily rooted in classical Islamic jurisprudence, which can be challenging to adapt to modern, pluralistic societies. Wael B. Hallaq contends that while Al-Mawardi's work was progressive for its time, it lacks the necessary flexibility to fully address the complexities of contemporary governance systems (Hallaq, 2009).

In addition to the characteristics of EL described in early Islam, Al-Māwardī added a new characteristic: focusing on community education and also related to the need for education of the elite: the Sultan, ministers and clerks, basing this education largely on the Qur'an, the Sunna and their interpretation. His rationale distinguished between education for present life and education for the afterlife, a perception that resembles that of EL in Catholic schools (Revel 2012). He argued that all knowledge and philosophy was legitimate because it enabled people to reach happiness, and that it should combine the study of core values with the acquisition of applicable tools. Yet he stressed the importance of religious knowledge above all other knowledge. He emphasised the need for sensitivity to learners' diversity, the importance of developing learners' motivation, gradual imparting of knowledge, freedom of thought and critical teaching and avoidance of blind imitation. His main criticism was 'not to exaggerate respect for the intelligent.' His vision for society embraced education to construct the ideal man emphasising the importance of education in forming opinions and seeing the intellect as the basis for education. A learned society would value knowledge and learning, embrace its wise men and not oppose their opinions (Al-Māwardī 1978, pp. 41–42)(Arar & Haj-Yehia, 2018)

Limitations And Challenges In Applying Al-Mawardi's Theories To Modern Political Contexts.

He laid intellectual foundations for the revival of the Abbasid Caliphate which is very likely to become even more widespread in the future. Most of these theories survive as theoretical discourse, because these theories have never been tested in reality. In many ways, especially in the context of modern democracy and politics, it is quite difficult to apply Al-Mawardi's concepts and thoughts as a whole. However, of course there will be some weaknesses or deficiencies that must be solved together, and the best solution is sought for the future. (Bayu Karunia Putra^{1*}, Azizatul Farhaini¹, Dinatul Aini¹, Siti Nurjannah¹, Noviana¹, Iza Martha Padila¹, Nanik Azizah¹, 2023)

Moreover, the application of Al-Mawardi's theories today is further complicated by several criticisms of the work traditionally attributed to him. Firstly, there are significant doubts about the true authorship of the *Naṣīḥat al-Mulūk*. Dr. Fu'ad 'Abd al-Mun'im Ahmad notably rejects Al-Mawardi's authorship, proposing instead that the work may have been written by Abu Zayd Ahmad b. Sahl al-Balkhi. This argument is thoroughly discussed in the introduction to Ahmad's edition and further elaborated upon in a separate publication. Secondly, there is substantial internal evidence indicating that the book may have originated during the Samanid period, with potential later additions or modifications. This evidence challenges the traditional attribution to Al-Mawardi. Lastly, the analysis of the manuscript itself adds to the skepticism. The surviving copy of the NM does not identify the author, patron, or intended recipient. The traditional attribution to Al-Mawardi appears to be more of a generic designation rather than the actual author's chosen name for the work. These points collectively raise critical questions about the true origins and authorship of the work, adding another layer of complexity to the challenge of adapting his theories to modern contexts (Marlow, 2007).

These issues of authorship and historical context are compounded by further criticisms of Al-Mawardi's theories, which highlight inherent limitations and challenges in applying them to modern political settings. Wafaa Wahba criticizes al-Māwardī for compromising by reducing the number of candidates to a single individual, which opens up the risk of

hereditary selection and authoritarian rule. Hamilton Gibb further critiques al-Māwardī for failing to provide a clear method for the legitimate deposition of a leader, arguing that al-Māwardī adheres to Sunni political principles but lacks an authoritative view or precedents for deposing a leader. This failure creates a dilemma characteristic of Sunni political thought at that time. Al-Māwardī only mentions the possibility of a leader's disqualification if he fails to implement justice or is physically unfit, which leaves a gap in the practical application of his theories. Although historical accounts of public complaint systems and petitions to contest the actions of Seljuk kings exist, suggesting that some mechanisms were in practice, al-Māwardī's work did not fully develop or theorize these methods. Additionally, al-Māwardī favors the Sunni political principle of tolerating oppressive rulers to avoid causing fitna (chaos), quoting a Prophetic narration that advises obedience to rulers, even if they are sinful, as long as their commands are not against Allah's commands. This principle further solidifies the authoritarian inclination criticized in his work. Gibb argues that the failure to develop robust methods for the deposition of leaders is not unique to al-Māwardī but is a broader issue in Sunni political thought up to his time, indicating a general reluctance or inability within Sunni jurisprudence to effectively challenge political authority (Whyte, 2019).

Furthermore, another significant aspect of the criticism surrounding Al-Mawardi's work lies in his approach towards apostasy and the *istitdba*. The first two authors to argue in favour of the renouncement of *istitdba* in certain cases of apostasy were the Shafi'i jurist al-Mawardi (d. 450/1058) and his Hanbali contemporary Abu Ya'la b. al-Farra' (d. 458/1066), both writing in the middle of the fifth/eleventh century. It seems to be the case that the two more tolerant schools of law, the Hanafis and the Shafi'is, were increasingly influenced by attempts within the Hanbali school in Baghdad to use the judgement against apostates as a means to persecute heterodoxy. A second influence must be considered from the Maliki tradition which never accepted the necessary application of the *istitdba*. Both al-Mawardi and Abu Ya'la were influential figures at the court and the chancellery of the caliph al-Qa'im, al-Qadir's successor in Baghdad, and their views reflect the legal thinking at court. This change in legal reasoning was probably influenced by the

successful second and third wave of the Ismaili da'wa in Iraq and Iran. Al-Ghazali's writings go far beyond these two authors and he may be regarded as the ultimate stage in this development towards the application of the law on apostates against state enemies.(Griffel, 2001)

Autocratic Tendencies

“An important scholar ‘Jasser Auda’ writes: 'Al-Mawardi legitimized the Abbasid tribal and monarchic system, which he found most excellent at his time, through his book al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyya.... Al-Mawardi ‘interpreted’ the scripts to imply ‘protecting people with noble lineage’ [such as Abbasids] from having a governor over them unless he comes from more noble roots, ‘legitimizing a caliph who is appointed by another of his own’, ‘giving people money from the trust according to their tribal lineages’, and giving the caliph the right to ‘have a monopoly over decision making’ (al-istibdad bi al-amr).”(Bhat, 2023)

“Al-Mawardi often considered dialectical views in his writings, whose example can be seen in his writing about caliph (Muslim ruler), in which he discusses the need of a caliph according to reason, while also consider the viewpoint according to Islamic rule (Shariah) (Borrut, 2006). Despite this, most of his writings are heavily influenced by Shariah (divine law) which focuses on implementing the law under the guidance of Islamic law. Furthermore, he described the criteria for selecting a caliph which described the characteristics of a desirable caliph while also nudging on the side of one of the dynasties that happened to be a part of the power struggle at that time (Madelung, 1997). In addition to this, his written text may explore diverse ideas but supported the claims which supported Muslim ruler, and in some accounts, it can be observed that the claims he established seem to remove accountability from caliphs while removing legal checks from them by merely adapting to the archaic notion of absolute monarchy which supported the caliph at all cost and even to the point of neglecting shariah (divine law).”(Abbasi, 2021)

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi’s emphasis on the centralization of power in the hands of a just and pious ruler has been criticized for its potential to

justify autocratic governance. Scholars like Bernard Lewis argue that while Al-Mawardi aimed to ensure justice and stability, his framework does not provide sufficient checks and balances against the abuse of power. This aspect of his thought can be seen as problematic in promoting democratic governance models, which require robust mechanisms for accountability and the separation of powers (Lewis, 1988).

In conclusion, while Al-Mawardi's works are foundational in Islamic political thought, they are not without their limitations. His emphasis on classical jurisprudence, insufficient attention to gender equality, and challenges in aligning with modern human rights standards highlight areas where his philosophy may fall short in addressing contemporary governance issues. These criticisms underscore the need for ongoing reinterpretation and adaptation of Islamic political principles to meet the demands of modern, pluralistic societies.

CONCLUSION

Al-Mawardi's enduring legacy offers valuable insights into governance, international relations, and ethical leadership, providing a rich source of inspiration and guidance for navigating contemporary global challenges. His work continues to inspire scholars and practitioners, fostering a dialogue on governance, ethics, and justice that is both rooted in Islamic tradition and responsive to modern realities.

Al-Mawardi's contributions to Islamic political thought and jurisprudence remain profoundly influential in shaping the discourse on ethical governance and societal welfare within the Islamic tradition and beyond. His nuanced exploration of governance principles, the responsibilities of leadership, and the importance of justice and public welfare provide a timeless framework that resonates with contemporary efforts to address complex global issues. Through his emphasis on adaptability, moral integrity, and the collective good, Al-Mawardi's ideas offer a foundational basis for developing governance models that are ethical, sustainable, and inclusive.

In today's interconnected world, where the challenges of governance, social inequality, and international cooperation are ever-present, Al-Mawardi's

philosophical insights into the balance between authority and accountability, the ethical dimensions of leadership, and the importance of dialogue and mutual respect among diverse communities serve as a beacon for constructive engagement and policy-making. His work not only enriches the ongoing scholarly examination of Islamic political theory but also provides practical considerations for contemporary governance, emphasizing the relevance of Islamic ethical principles in addressing the dilemmas of modernity.

Furthermore, Al-Mawardi's perspective on international relations and the conduct of diplomacy underscores the potential for Islamic political thought to contribute to a more harmonious global order. His recognition of the value of cultural exchange and mutual understanding between civilizations highlights the importance of fostering international cooperation and dialogue in an era marked by global challenges that require collective action.

As we move forward, the enduring legacy of Al-Mawardi reminds us of the importance of grounding governance and leadership in ethical principles and the pursuit of justice. His work continues to inspire a critical reflection on how Islamic tradition can inform responses to contemporary issues, encouraging a dynamic interplay between historical wisdom and modern governance needs. In sum, Al-Mawardi's contributions stand as a testament to the enduring relevance of Islamic political thought in navigating the complexities of the contemporary world, offering valuable lessons on the synthesis of tradition and modernity in the pursuit of a just and equitable society.

REFERENCES

- Afsaruddin, A. (2005). *The First Muslims: History and Memory*. Oneworld Publications.
- Ahmed, K. (2004). *Islamic Law and the Challenges of Modernity*. AltaMira Press.
- Ahmed, L. (1992). *Women and Gender in Islam: Historical Roots of a Modern Debate*. Yale University Press.
- An-Na'im, A. A. (2008). *Islam and the Secular State: Negotiating the Future of Shari'a*. Harvard University Press.

- Black, A. (2001). *The History of Islamic Political Thought: From the Prophet to the Present*. Routledge.
- Bunt, G. R. (2003). *Islam in the Digital Age: E-Jihad, Online Fatwas, and Cyber Islamic Environments*. Pluto Press.
- Bunt, G. R. (2009). *iMuslims: Rewiring the House of Islam*. The University of North Carolina Press.
- Crone, P. (2004). *God's Rule: Government and Islam*. Columbia University Press.
- Crone, P., & Hinds, M. (1986). *God's Caliph: Religious Authority in the First Centuries of Islam*. Cambridge University Press.
- El-Gamal, M. A. (2006). *Islamic Finance: Law, Economics, and Practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Esposito, J. L. (2010). *The Future of Islam*. Oxford University Press.
- Hallaq, W. (2009). *Shari'a: Theory, Practice, Transformations*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hallaq, W. B. (1997). *A history of Islamic legal theories: An introduction to Sunni usul al-fiqh*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hallaq, W. B. (2009). *An Introduction to Islamic Law*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hayat, U. (2013). *Social impact investing and Islamic finance: Where can paths cross?* CFA Institute.
- Johnson, J. T. (2007). *Ethics and War in Comparative Religious Perspective*. Ashgate.
- Kahf, M. (1997). *The Islamic Economy: Analytical Study of the Functioning of the Islamic Economic System*. Dar Al-Fikr.
- Kamali, M. H. (1997). *Freedom, Equality, and Justice in Islam*. Islamic Texts Society.
- Kennedy, H. (2004). *The Prophet and the Age of the Caliphates: The Islamic Near East from the 6th to the 11th Century*. Pearson Education Limited.
- Khadduri, M. (1987). *The Islamic Conception of Justice*. The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Khan, M. A. (2011). *Islamic Democratic Discourse: Theory, Debates, and Philosophical Perspectives*. Lexington Books.

- Kuran, T. (2011). *The Long Divergence: How Islamic Law Held Back the Middle East*. Princeton University Press.
- Lambton, A. K. S. (1981). *State and government in medieval Islam: An introduction to the study of Islamic political theory: The jurists*. Oxford University Press.
- Lapidus, I. M. (2002). *A History of Islamic Societies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Sachedina, A. (2009). *Islamic Biomedical Ethics: Principles and Application*. Oxford University Press.
- Saeed, A. (2006). *Islamic Thought: An Introduction*. Routledge.
- Vikør, K. S. (2005). *Between God and the Sultan: A History of Islamic Law*. Oxford University Press.
- Wilson, R. (2006). *Islam and Economic Policy*. Edinburgh University Press.

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RELEVANCE OF ISLAMIC TRADITIONAL PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES IN 21ST CENTURY EDUCATION: A CASE STUDY OF AL-QARAWIYYIN UNIVERSITY

MD MAHMUD¹, SHIBLY SADIK²

ABSTRACT

The University of Al-Qarawiyyin is renowned as the most ancient and historic academic institution in the world. This university offers a conventional teaching method in the present day, which presents a significant challenge in the 21st century. How is this pedagogy still advantageous for human beings? How does it contribute to mental or intellectual development? This study report intends to investigate the efficacy of conventional teaching for human beings. For this paper, I want to engage in discussions with others, with the aim of exchanging and acquiring information via research articles. Traditional pedagogy promotes the development of close relationships between instructors and students, fosters the acquisition of skills and critical thinking, emphasizes memorization and spoken communication, and enhances attention and group debate. Al-Qarawiyyin University adheres to a traditional pedagogy

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in order to impart religious teachings and promote the authentic principles of Islam.

KEYWORDS: Islamic Pedagogy, Pedagogical strategies, 21st century, University of Al-Qarawiyyin.

INTRODUCTION

The University of Al-Qarawiyyin is widely acknowledged as the most ancient and continuously functioning educational establishment globally. It has a rich heritage deeply anchored in the traditions of madrasah-style instruction. Throughout the ages, the notion of the university has undergone substantial transformations, adjusting to shifts in both time and geographical context. However, it has constantly maintained its fundamental objective of seeking truth via the examination of evidence. The university's dedication to truth continues to be a fundamental aspect of its character, despite its evolving role in pursuing larger functional objectives in the contemporary day (Ali, 2016).

Al-Qarawiyyin University has the challenge of maintaining its traditional teaching techniques while also adapting to the requirements of modern education. The university's goal, centred on the search for evidence-based truth, now encompasses a broader responsibility of promoting critical thinking, innovation, and global involvement. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, a university is defined as a "corporation of teachers and students established to provide and receive instruction in a specific range of subjects that goes beyond what is offered at a school." An institution of higher education is a recognised establishment that provides courses and research opportunities mostly in non-vocational disciplines. It has established authorities and privileges, including the authority to grant degrees. Modern universities, such as Al-Qarawiyyin, have a wider range of obligations that go beyond vocational training. They are expected to provide a complete education, encourage intellectual exploration, and contribute to the progress of society (Hoque & Md. Faruk Abdullah, 2021).

As Al-Qarawiyyin University progresses, it must include contemporary teaching methodologies and technology while maintaining its

dedication to conventional principles and the pursuit of knowledge. This entails revising its curriculum to include current fields of study, cultivating an all-encompassing and varied academic atmosphere, and promoting research and advancement. By doing this, Al-Qarawiyyin not only pays tribute to its historical function as a stronghold of education but also adjusts to the difficulties and possibilities of the 21st century, guaranteeing its continued importance and relevance as an institution in the worldwide academic sphere. Al-Qarawiyyin University acts as a conduit between its historical legacy and the progressive future, persistently imparting knowledge and motivation to successive cohorts of global students (Hardaker et al., 2013).

CURRENT EDUCATIONAL PROBLEMS

The present educational system has seen major developments that result in the founding of many colleges and educational institutions. It does not, however, help students to develop with a complete and balanced set of character qualities. Students nowadays are dealing with a variety of problems including stress, poor critical thinking ability, and low emotional intelligence. These issues not only influence individual students but also have wider consequences for society as a good education system loses the possibility to benefit everyone (Gottfredson et al., 2004).

Academic corruption is one of the most serious issues. Schools and universities now abound in instances of academic lying including plagiarism and cheating. Forced by pressure to get good marks, students may turn to dishonest methods, therefore compromising the integrity of the educational system. The convenient access to knowledge available on the internet has aggravated this issue by allowing students to replicate work without appropriate credit easier. This not only undermines real academic success but also stunts students' growth in ethical behaviour and critical thinking (Berkley Center for Religion, 2015; Mohrman et al., 2011).

Important issues within the educational system also include respect and discipline. The respect kids have for classmates and instructors has clearly dropped. Common in schools are more instances of disruptive behaviour, bullying, and disrespect of authorities. This contempt disturbs the learning

process and generates a poisonous environment unfit for the expansion of education. Overwhelmed with disciplinary problems, teachers may struggle to maintain a calm and efficient classroom (Berkley Center for Religion, 2015).

Critics claim that these problems belong to the educational system. Previous researchers have tackled many issues including antiquated teaching methods, a dearth of qualified teachers, and delayed availability of curricular resources. Furthermore attacked for failing to meet the many learning demands of children and stifling of creativity is the emphasis on standardised testing. Further aggravating these issues are insufficient mental health care, a dearth of practical life skills instruction, and few chances for personal development (Mizikaci, 2006).

Furthermore, the digital gap is becoming increasingly noticeable, therefore many pupils lack access to required technical tools. This disparity in educational chances helps to maintain social and financial inequalities. Therefore, the educational system has to be completely reformed to handle these many difficulties so that it not only provides intellectual knowledge but also guarantees well-rounded, emotionally aware, and socially conscious people. Developing an education system that not only discourages academic dishonesty and fosters respect and discipline but also gives students the tools and values they need to succeed in a world fast changing (Huang et al., 2018; Lindsay, 2005; Reisdorf & Rikard, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical Role of Islamic Universities

Table 1 is a comprehensive summary of the prominent Islamic colleges that have played an important part in history. It includes information on their founding, geographical location, and noteworthy contributions and influences. The “University Details” column consolidates the university’s name, founding date, and country of location. The “Notable Roles and Impacts” section showcases the significant achievements of each institution in several subjects, including philosophy, medicine, and religion. It also emphasises their impact on both the Islamic world and worldwide intellectual traditions. This approach

provides a succinct but thorough examination of the historical importance of these major educational institutions.

Table 1: Historical Role of Islamic Universities

University Details	Notable Roles and Impacts
Al-Qarawiyyin University, 859 CE, Morocco (Hoque & Md. Faruk Abdullah, 2021)	Played a vital part in the translation movement, safeguarded information from ancient writings, and had impact on subjects such as medicine, philosophy, and religion. It is the oldest educational institution that has been running without interruption.
Al-Azhar University, 970-972 CE, Egypt (Mohamed Abdel Fattah, 2019)	Renowned for its extensive program including Islamic law, theology, and sciences. It emerged as a prominent establishment in the Islamic realm, exerting influence on religious and scholarly ideas.
University of al-Andalus, Late 9th century, Spain (Daud, 2014)	During the Islamic Golden Age, this place had a crucial role as a hub for intellectual and cultural interchange. It made substantial contributions to fields like as philosophy, medicine, and the arts.
Nizamiyya (Baghdad), 1065 CE, Iraq (Hardaker et al., 2013)	Founded by Nizam al-Mulk, it had a significant impact in disseminating Sunni Islamic doctrines and legal principles. The institution drew renowned academics and played a crucial role in defining Islamic education.
Al-Mustansiriya School, 1227-1233 CE, Iraq	Served as a prominent hub for several academic fields, making substantial contributions to Islamic research

University Details	Notable Roles and Impacts
	and legal studies. Additionally, it had one of the first hospitals dedicated to medical education.
Al-Nizamiyya of Nishapur, 11th century, Iran	Significantly contributed to the development and widespread dissemination of Islamic law and theology. It was a component of the wider network of Nizamiyya institutions that influenced the education system in mediaeval Islamic societies.

History of Al-Qarawiyyin

Founded by Fatima Al-Fihri in 859 CE in Fez, Morocco, Al-Qarawiyyin institution is the oldest continually running institution in the world. Originally from Tunisia, Fatima was a rich lady who built a mosque from her fortune; subsequently, the mosque housed the university's headquarters. The university's emphasis moved over time from religious studies to include a broad spectrum of disciplines including astronomy, medicine, languages, grammar, mathematics, and music. Al-Qarawiyyin therefore developed into a gathering place for academics from all across the globe, thereby promoting a rich intellectual climate. Furthermore, the institution was very important in translating Greek books into Arabic, therefore supporting the European Renaissance. Scholars such Ibn Khaldun, Ibn Arabi, Averroes (Ibn Rushd), and Moses Maimonides studied there, therefore influencing many spheres of knowledge (Ali, 2016; Hoque & Md. Faruk Abdullah, 2021).

Al-Qarawiyyin University also received assistance from Fatima's personal fortune, sultan contributions, and a Waqf system wherein individuals paid money or property to help the university. Later, this kind of financing affected the creation of endowment systems at European colleges such as Oxford. Al-Qarawiyyin institution is now acknowledged by UNESCO and the Guinness World Records as the oldest institution worldwide. The institution, with Fatima Al-Fihri's legacy spanning millennia as evidence of the value of

education and intellectual development, still running as a hub of knowledge despite its ancient beginnings (Hardaker et al., 2013).

Traditional Pedagogical Methods in the Past

Traditional teaching has several advantages that make it relevant in contemporary times. It has a lengthy track record of effectively transmitting information and skills from one generation to the next. This approach offers a distinct framework, facilitating pupils' concentration and maintaining their organization. Furthermore, conventional teaching methods often include cultural aspects, which help to uphold traditions and foster a sense of individual and collective identity. The familiarity of these strategies fosters a conducive and reassuring learning environment. Additionally, the focus on rote memorization cultivates a solid basis of information. Teachers provide direct guidance to pupils, delivering prompt comments and assistance (Lovtsova et al., 2021).

Memorization is a fundamental element of conventional teaching methods. Students often commit information, formulae, and language to memory. Although this strategy may not consistently foster profound comprehension, it is beneficial in disciplines such as mathematics, language acquisition, and history. In these regions, the process of committing information to memory serves as the fundamental foundation for acquiring more intricate knowledge. Furthermore, conventional teaching methods promote the development of deep connections with literature. Engaging in active reading, participating in conversations, and completing writing projects contribute to the enhancement of comprehension (Mccarthy, 2011).

In addition, conventional teaching methods foster critical thinking by integrating a range of tactics. These methods include inquiry, Socratic discourse, and problem-based learning. These strategies promote students' ability to critically analyse, assess, and integrate knowledge. By engaging in this process, students develop the aptitude required to address intricate problems and provide well-informed judgements (Mascolo, 2009).

Conventional teaching methods can provide a well-organized educational setting. This framework helps pupils in comprehending the content effortlessly. The package comprises explicit lesson plans, concise topic introductions, ample practice opportunities, and comprehensive review materials. This approach guarantees that students acquire essential principles prior to on to more complex subjects. Traditional pedagogy is characterised by teacher-centered education. Teachers serve as the main purveyors of information and oversee the whole of the learning process. This method, albeit organized, enables prompt elucidation of ideas (Chakera et al., 2020).

Traditional techniques provide a sense of familiarity for both students and instructors, ensuring a consistent learning experience. Additionally, they contribute to the preservation of cultural values and customs, ensuring their transmission from one generation to the next. Conventional evaluations, such as quizzes and examinations, are well-suited to these instructional approaches. They provide transparent assessment standards and valuable feedback on student advancement. This alignment guarantees that the objectives of education are achieved efficiently (Lovtsova et al., 2021).

Shortcomings of the Traditional Pedagogical Methods

Table 2 presents the main flaws of conventional teaching strategies along with a thorough explanation of every one of them. Although it works well in certain situations, traditional education sometimes stresses rote memorization and a teacher-centered approach, which could impede the development of critical thinking abilities and lower student involvement. While overemphasizing memorization might lead to superficial knowledge rather than deep comprehension, the rigidity of conventional approaches may not fit the many learning styles and demands of all pupils. Furthermore, conventional teaching might show cultural prejudice, therefore marginalizing many points of view and restricting inclusiveness. Furthermore, limiting possibilities for interactive and creative learning experiences are the low utilization of technology in these approaches. Finally, emphasizing more memorization than on the application

and synthesis of information, old tests often coincide poorly with current educational goals.

Table 2: Shortcomings of the Traditional Pedagogical Methods

Shortcomings	Description
Lack of Critical Thinking Development (Saleh, 2001)	Conventional teaching approaches may give rote memorization top priority above the growth in critical thinking ability. This method reduces pupils' capacity for analysis, evaluation, and synthesis of data—qualities necessary for tackling difficult situations and guiding choices.
Teacher-Centered Approach (Jory, 2011)	With conventional approaches emphasizing the instructor as the main source of information, pupils may have a passive learning experience. This strategy may discourage active engagement and restrict chances for students to take responsibility for their learning given little student input and interaction.
Limited Student Engagement (Nces, 2023)	Because of their typically strict and one-size-fits-all attitude, traditional educational approaches might produce poor student involvement. Particularly if the content is not delivered in a manner that is relevant or meaningful to the students, students may get bored or disengaged, therefore lowering their general learning results and motivation.
Inflexibility	Many times, traditional teaching is rigid and unadaptable to satisfy the various demands of students. For pupils who need a more customised or unique approach to learning, it may not fit various learning styles, speeds, or talents, therefore less successful.

Shortcomings	Description
Overemphasis on Memorization (Chakera et al., 2020)	Although memorising is a fundamental part of conventional education, too much focus on rote learning might result in a surface-level knowledge of ideas. While students may be able to remember facts and statistics, they may find it difficult to apply this information in useful or real-world circumstances, therefore impeding more thorough understanding and critical application of abilities.
Cultural Bias	Conventional approaches might unintentionally support certain cultural standards, beliefs, or viewpoints, therefore marginalising pupils from many origins. Lack of representation and inclusion in the curriculum resulting from this might make it more difficult for every student to see themselves reflected in their education and have a feeling of belonging.
Limited Use of Technology (Ramdhan et al., 2025)	Modern technology is often underused in traditional teaching methods, which might restrict chances for interactive and creative learning environments. These approaches could overlook improving student involvement, cooperation, and access to a wider spectrum of knowledge and viewpoints by not completely merging digital tools and resources.
Assessment Misalignment	Conventional tests and quizzes, for example, often place more emphasis on memorizing and recall than on comprehension, application, and synthesis of information. This may cause a mismatch between what is taught and assessed, therefore limiting the assessment of student learning and development.

Application of Current Methods in Teaching Learning

Table 3 shows some contemporary teaching and learning strategies extensively used in modern education. These techniques stress a change from conventional teacher-centered approaches to more student-centered, participatory models.

While Blended Learning and the Flipped Classroom mix digital resources with conventional education, giving flexibility and deeper interaction with the content, Student-Centered Learning emphasises specific student needs and promotes active involvement. Through integrating students in real-world projects and group work, Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Collaborative Learning foster critical thinking, creativity, and cooperation. Gamification gives the learning process game components, therefore increasing its appeal and motivational power. Encouragement of inquiry-based learning helps students to be curious and autonomous explorers, therefore empowering them to assume leadership of their education. While Technology-Enhanced Learning uses digital technologies to improve engagement and provide individualised learning experiences, Differentiated Instruction guarantees that various learning requirements are satisfied by customising methods to particular individuals. By addressing the many requirements of today's students, these approaches taken together reflect a more dynamic, inclusive, and interesting approach to education.

Table 3: Application of Current Methods in Teaching Learning

Current Method	Application in Teaching and Learning
Student-Centered Learning (Mascolo, 2009; Shanmugavelu et al., 2020; Trabelsi et al., 2023)	Student-Centered Learning Emphasizes pupils' needs, interests, and preferred learning approaches. Promotes ownership of the learning process, teamwork, and active involvement. Teachers guide students in investigating subjects and enhancing their critical thinking abilities, therefore acting as facilitators.

Current Method	Application in Teaching and Learning
Blended Learning (Hennessy et al., 2022; Kilipiris et al., 2024; Rabbi et al., 2018)	Blended Learning Mixes online learning with conventional classroom training. gives pupils freedom to study at their own speed and access to a large spectrum of digital materials. This approach may be customised to fit each student's particular requirement and facilitates customised education.
Flipped Classroom (Kilipiris et al., 2024; Ruiz-Jiménez et al., 2022)	Flipped Classroom Delivers teaching materials—often online—outside of the classroom, therefore reversing the conventional learning setting. Hands-on activities, conversations, and knowledge application during classroom time let students really interact with the content and work with teachers and classmates.
Project-Based Learning (PBL) (Trust et al., 2023)	Project-Based Learning Engages pupils in practical projects requiring them to use knowledge and abilities to address challenges. promotes cooperation, critical thought, and invention. Often leading to a more meaningful educational experience, PBL gives students chances to pursue their interests and participate actively in their learning.
Collaborative Learning (Borthwick & Gallagher-Brett, 2014; Davis et al., 2016; Hong & Sullivan, 2013)	Collaborative Learning invites students to cooperate in small groups towards shared objectives. This approach improves coordination, communication, and ability to solve problems. Through student learning from one another and developing a feeling of

Current Method	Application in Teaching and Learning
	community, cooperative learning helps to create a supportive classroom.
Gamification (Hossain & Rahman, 2023; Kilipiris et al., 2024; Ruiz-Jiménez et al., 2022)	Gamification includes point scoring, leaderboards, and rewards—game components—into the educational process. Gamification makes learning enjoyable and engaging, therefore boosting engagement and drive. It may also inspire pupils to aim for both intellectual and personal development and foster fair competition.
Inquiry-Based Learning (Khalaf & Zin, 2018; Tezcan-Unal et al., 2018)	Inquiry-Based Learning invites students to probe subjects in great detail, ask questions, and do research. This approach increases knowledge of the topic, critical thinking, and curiosity. Through inquiry-based learning, students may participate actively in their education and grow in ability for autonomous research and analysis.
Differentiated Instruction (Jordan & McGhie-Richmond, 2014)	Teachers use tools and approaches based on the varied demands of their pupils. Differentiated teaching guarantees that every student has access to the curriculum and may realise their full potential by allowing several learning styles, talents, and interests. It usually calls for many strategies, including flexible groups and tiered tasks.
Technology-Enhanced Learning (Khalaf & Zin, 2018; Shrestha, 2013)	Technology-Enhanced Learning incorporates into the learning process digital technologies and resources. This approach improves involvement, teamwork, and information availability.

Current Method	Application in Teaching and Learning
	Personalised learning experiences—where students may investigate subjects, practise skills, and get immediate feedback via applications, simulations, and online platforms—are made possible by technology.

DISCUSSION

Relevance of Al Qarawiyyin University in 21st century

Al-Qarawiyyin University is very relevant in the twenty-first century as it is the oldest continually running educational institution in the world with great historical heritage. The institution struggles to properly integrate technology into its instructional system as it tries to modify its conventional pedagogical approaches to current needs. Improving the educational process and guaranteeing that students are ready to negotiate a world becoming more and more digital depend on this integration. Al-Qarawiyyin can create a dynamic and adaptable learning environment by fusing modern tools such online learning platforms, digital materials, and interactive technology with conventional teaching approaches. This strategy not only protects the cultural legacy of the school but also satisfies the many demands of the modern global students, thereby arming them to succeed in many spheres of work and study.

Another important component of Al-Qarawiyyin University's development is changing the syllabus to stay current in the contemporary society. The institution has to reconcile keeping its historical concentration on religious and cultural studies with adding modern disciplines such science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). Furthermore included are approaches like Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Inquiry-Based Learning, which help to develop critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities—qualities necessary to meet difficult worldwide problems. Equally crucial is encouraging inclusion and diversity in the curriculum and student

population so that the educational resources are easily available and mirror a broad spectrum of viewpoints. This inclusion not only enhances the academic atmosphere but also helps students to have a better awareness of world problems, therefore arming them to significantly contribute to a linked world.

Al-Qarawiyyin University has to additionally concentrate on educational quality, accessibility, and faculty growth if it is to remain a top educational institution. Programs for ongoing professional development may provide teachers with contemporary pedagogical approaches, therefore improving their capacity to give excellent, student-centered education. By giving scholarships, financial assistance, and technology-enhanced learning tools to help students from all socioeconomic backgrounds, the institution should also encourage accessibility and equality. Maintaining the school at the forefront of global education depends on supporting research and innovation, therefore promoting a culture of intellectual curiosity drawing academics from all across the globe. At last, improving community involvement helps Al-Qarawiyyin to match its educational initiatives with modern society demands, thereby giving students chances to use their knowledge in practical settings. By means of these initiatives, Al-Qarawiyyin University may keep carrying out its historic role while developing to meet the demands of the twenty-first century, thereby linking its rich history with a creative future.

CONCLUSION

Al-Qarawiyyin University is evidence of the continuing value of education as it combines its rich historical history with the needs of the present society. The university has to include technology, change its course, and promote diversity as it negotiates the difficulties of the twenty-first century to make sure it stays relevant and successful in the global scene of today. Al-Qarawiyyin may keep fostering among its pupils critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities by keeping a dedication to educational quality, accessibility, and ongoing professional development. Moreover, the university may go beyond the classroom by supporting research, creativity, and community involvement, thus answering modern society demands and supporting the worldwide information sharing. By means of these initiatives, Al-Qarawiyyin University

not only pays tribute to its historical significance as a lighthouse of knowledge but also presents itself as a crucial institution for next generations, thereby bridging the gap between legacy and modernity.

REFERENCE

- Ali, A. bin H. (2016). *The Qarawiyyin University and Its Role in History*. Berkley Center for Religion. (2015). *Faith and Development in Focus: Bangladesh. March*, 1–129. <http://berkeleycenter.org>
- Borthwick, K., & Gallagher-Brett, A. (2014). “Inspiration, ideas, encouragement”: teacher development and improved use of technology in language teaching through open educational practice. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 27(2), 163–183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2013.818560>
- Chakera, S., Haffner, D., & Harrop, E. (2020). *Structured Pedagogy: For Real-Time Equitable Improvements in Learning Outcomes* (Issue June). <https://www.unicef.org/esa/media/7511/file/ESA-Structured-Pedagogy-2020.pdf>
- Daud, A. H. M. (2014). *Andalusia to Revival Western World*. 14(5), 14–24.
- Davis, E., Cochran, D., Fagerheim, B., & Thoms, B. (2016). Enhancing Teaching and Learning: Libraries and Open Educational Resources in the Classroom. *Public Services Quarterly*, 12(1), 22–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228959.2015.1108893>
- Gottfredson, D. C., Gerstenblith, S. A., Soulé, D. A., Womer, S. C., & Lu, S. (2004). Do after school programs reduce delinquency? *Prevention Science*, 5(4), 253–266. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:PREV.0000045359.41696.02>
- Hardaker, G., Ahmad, A., & Hardaker, G. (2013). *An insight into Islamic pedagogy at the University of al-Qarawiyyin*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17504971211236308>
- Hennessy, S., D’Angelo, S., McIntyre, N., Koomar, S., Kreimeia, A., Cao, L., Brugha, M., & Zubairi, A. (2022). Technology Use for Teacher Professional Development in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A systematic review. *Computers and Education Open*, 3(December 2021), 100080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cao.2022.100080>
- Hong, A. H., & Sullivan, F. R. (2013). Towards an idea-centered, principle-base design to as creation approach support learning knowledge. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 57(5), 613–627. <https://doi.org/10.1007/sl>
- Hoque, M. N., & Md. Faruk Abdullah. (2021). *The World’s Oldest University And Its Financing Experience: A Study On Al-Qarawiyyin University*

- (859-990). *Journal of Nusantara Studies* 2021, 6(1), 24–41.
- Hossain, M. M., & Rahman, M. A. (2023). Teaching English amidst coronavirus pandemic in Bangladesh: Technological adaptations and pedagogical modifications. *EnJourMe (English Journal of Merdeka) : Culture, Language, and Teaching of English*, 8(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.26905/enjourme.v8i1.10186>
- Huang, G., Li, X., Chen, W., & Straubhaar, J. D. (2018). Fall-Behind Parents? The Influential Factors on Digital Parenting Self-Efficacy in Disadvantaged Communities. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 62(9), 1186–1206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764218773820>
- Jordan, A., & McGhie-Richmond, D. (2014). Identifying effective teaching practices in inclusive classrooms. *International Perspectives on Inclusive Education*, 3, 133–162. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-363620140000003023>
- Jory, K. B. P. (2011). Salafi Madrasahs and Islamic Radicalism in Post-New Order Indonesia. In *Islamic Studies and Islamic Education*. <http://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:238095/IslamicStudiesandIslamicEducation.pdf&force=1#page=123>
- Khalaf, B. K., & Zin, Z. B. M. (2018). Traditional and inquiry-based learning pedagogy: A systematic critical review. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 545–564. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.11434a>
- Kilipiris, F., Avdimiotis, S., Christou, E., Tragouda, A., & Konstantinidis, I. (2024). Bloom's Taxonomy Student Persona Responses to Blended Learning Methods Employing the Metaverse and Flipped Classroom Tools. *Education Sciences*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14040418>
- Lindsay, C. (2005). Employability, services for unemployed job seekers and the digital divide. *Urban Studies*, 42(2), 325–339. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098042000316173>
- Lovtsova, I. V., Burovkina, L. A., & Sheshko, A. S. (2021). Preservation of the intangible cultural heritage through the implementation of additional general education programs in the field of fine arts. *Revista Tempos e Espaços Em Educação*, 14(33), e15929. <https://doi.org/10.20952/revtee.v14i33.15929>
- Mascolo, M. (2009). Beyond student-centered and teacher-centered pedagogy: Teaching and learning as guided participation. *Pedagogy and the Human Sciences*, 1(1), 3–27.
- Mccarthy, M. (2011). Aligning learning outcomes , learning activities and assessment . *Seminario Internacional SCT, August*, 2–4.
- Mizikaci, F. (2006). A systems approach to program evaluation model for quality in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 14(1), 37–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09684880610643601>

- Mohamed Abdel Fattah. (2019). Higher Islamic Education and the Development of Intellectualism in Egypt: Case study of Al-Azhar Education System. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*, 2(5).
- Mohrman, K., Wang, Y., & Li, X. (2011). Quality assurance in undergraduate education: Transformation of higher education policy in china. In *International Perspectives on Education and Society* (Vol. 15). Emerald Group Publishing Ltd. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-3679\(2011\)0000015016](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1479-3679(2011)0000015016)
- Nces. (2023). *Teachers' Reports of Disruptive Student Behaviors and Staff Rule Enforcement*. 1–6.
- Rabbi, M. M. F., Zakaria, A. K. M., & Tonmoy, M. M. (2018). Teaching listening skill through Google Classroom: A study at tertiary level in Bangladesh. *DUET Journal*, 3(1), 2–7. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324561428>
- Ramdzan, Z., Hamzah, M. I., & Zulkifli, H. (2025). -century learning in islamic education. 13(7), 4221–4231. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S07.529>
- Reisdorf, B. C., & Rikard, R. V. (2018). Digital Rehabilitation: A Model of Reentry Into the Digital Age. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 62(9), 1273–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764218773817>
- Ruiz-Jiménez, M. C., Martínez-Jiménez, R., Licerán-Gutiérrez, A., & García-Martí, E. (2022). Students' attitude: Key to understanding the improvement of their academic RESULTS in a flipped classroom environment. *International Journal of Management Education*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100635>
- Saleh, M. M. S. (2001). Developing a History Curriculum: An Islamic Perspective. *Intellectual Discourse*, 9(1), 85–100.
- Shanmugavelu, G., Parasuraman, B., Ariffin, K., Kannan, B., & Vadivelu, M. (2020). Inquiry Method in the Teaching and Learning Process. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(3), 6–9. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v8i3.2396>
- Shrestha, P. N. (2013). English language classroom practices: Bangladeshi primary school children's perceptions. *RELC Journal*, 44(2), 147–162. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688213488466>
- Tezcan-Unal, B., Winston, K., & Qualter, A. (2018). Learning-oriented quality assurance in higher education institutions. *Quality in Higher Education*, 24(3), 221–237. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2018.1558504>
- Trabelsi, Z., Alnajjar, F., Parambil, M. M. A., Gochoo, M., & Ali, L. (2023). Real-Time Attention Monitoring System for Classroom: A Deep Learning Approach for Student's Behavior Recognition. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 7(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc7010048>

Trust, T., Maloy, R. W., & Edwards, S. (2023). College student engagement in OER design projects: Impacts on attitudes, motivation, and learning. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 24(3), 353–371. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14697874221081454>

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AL-MAWARDI'S PARADIGMATIC THEORY OF POLITICS: IMAMAH OR KHILAPAH IN THEORY AND PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Abu al Hasan al Mawardi (364 - 450 AH/974 - 1058 CE) flourished at a time of political turmoil and instability during Abbasid Caliphate in Baghdad. He was one of the greatest of universal figurers in the history of Islamic culture and heritage. His unique and invaluable contribution was to develop the paradigmatic theory of politics of Imamah or Khilaphah mainly in terms of safeguarding religion for human justice and showed the rules of administration of government in detail. He was a jurist par-excellence, a great scholar, a political thinker, a philosopher and the statesman in true sense writing some of the most important books on Fiqh, Shariyah rules cum Administrative Law and politics who shed the lasting impact upon his contemporary and later thinkers equally. He was the man who made his age his own. Being the Qadhi-ul-Qujat he had to appoint and reject the other Qadhis in different districts and provinces in the Abbasid state and empire. He systematically formulated the paradigmatic theory of Imamah or Khilafah in juristic pattern in Sunni Islam

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on the precedents of the early Islam and its polity for the first time in Muslim political thought in his most monumental work entitled “Al Ahkam as Sultaniyyah– The Ordinances of Government “ in the mid 5th Hijra century. The Purpose of writing this book was to provide the contemporary khaliph(s) with the utmost attributes of a true Caliph individually for himself and the basic principles, rules and key provisions of justice to run the state - empire successfully, mainly coping with the then challenges coming from the Buwid’s Ameers who were the power in fact against the total Abbasid Caliphs. Hence, Al Mawardi’s prime aim was to integrate the administrative Power of the Vizierate and the Caliphate of the Islamic Empire and civilization to reach the purpose for which the Institution of Caliphate was first established in the Muslim Ummah. The objective of this paper is to examine the theory of Imamah or Khilafa of Al Mawardi and reveal the necessary aspects of it as understood universally in its true sense for an easy comprehension to the real contexts. The most of the research works and the journals, particularly on his political thought and philosophy written by both the orientalist and the Islamic scholars and thinkers particularly his “Ahkam” have been consulted. And the historical, analytical and qualitative approaches used for the development of this paper. His theory of the Imamah is one of many possible theories of government-as there is no any single theory or political system in Islam– is to say in Sunni Islam– for its ever space of dynamism in contexts.

KEYWORDS

Pragmatic Theory of Politics, Imamah or Khilaphah, Al Ahkam as Sultaniyyah– The Ordinances of Government, Buwid’s Ameers, Political system in Islam, Sunni Islam

INTRODUCTION

Two decades and a half after the death of the great philosopher, al- Farabi, al-Mawardi, an outstanding jurist was born in 364/974 in the city of Basra, one of the most famous centers of learning and education in the Islamic world during the middle age. al-Mawardi prepared himself to be a jurist under Abul Qasim Abdul Wahid al-Samari (d. 386 A.H) a learned theologian and a leading Shafi’te jurist under whom students from far off countries came to receive

instruction and learning knowledge. He proceeded afterwards to Baghdad to prosecute his studies further under Sheikh Abu Hamid al Isra'ini (d. 406). He also read with Abu-Muhammad Abdullah al Bafi (d.398 A.H) an eminent scholar, an eloquent speaker and learned theologian of Baghdad. Well versed in jurisprudence, grammar, literature, poetry al-Mawardi was well trained by his erudite teachers of his time and gradually prepared himself into a great personality, particularly, in the sciences of Hadith, Fiqh, Quranic commentary and Sirah of the holy prophet (sm.) (Mian, 1994). He was equally, proficient in the subject of literature, poetry, ethics, politics and administration. He, then began his active life as a professor of law and jurisprudence at Basrah and Baghdad and when his name and fame began to spread far and wide, he was made the chief justice of the Abbasid state-empire, on the title of Qadi-al-Qudat (Sharif, 1963). His biographers are profuse in their praises calling him the great, the high, the wonderful leader, one of the most prominent and biggest of the Shafi'ite savant and there is no doubt that there was none of his contemporaries who was more cognizant of the principles underline the Islamic state (Sherwani, 1985). He acted for the Caliph al-Qadirbillah (381-422-991-1031) in his negotiations with the Buwaihids and when in 429/1037 Jalal al Dawla Baha(d 435/1044) asked al Qaimbillah, the son and successor of Qadirbillah to give him the title of Shahinshah(the king of the kings). Al-Mawardi expressed his objections in a fatwa. He also carried out various missions for al-Qaimbillah(422-467/1031-1075) including one to the Seljuk Sultan Toghrilbeg in 435-61/1043-1045) (Lambton, 1981).

Al-Mawardi flourished at a time when political instability and turmoil and utter corruption prevailed in seat of the Abbassidee Caliph in Baghdad. The office of the caliphate had been declining for some time and the caliphs had become mere puppets in the hands of soldiers and adventures. The state was beset with dangers from within and without. The Fatimids had come to power in Tunisia in 909, and sixty years latter had concurred Egypt and offered the first serious challenge to the right of the Abbassidee to rule. Other threats were looming on the eastern front and closer to home. Some thirty years before the birth of al-Mawardi, the fortunes of the Buwaihids – a Shi'ite Persian family of army commanders-had begun to rise and he lived to see there down

fall as a result of internal dissension and continuous revolt. For most of his life time they wielded real power in Baghdad, appointing and removing caliphs at will, at times throwing them in jail or going to grotesque extremes in punishing them (Al-Mawardi, 2006). At this situation al-Mawardi's integrity was never in doubt. He enjoyed the respect and trust of caliphs and Buwaihids alike, both of whom restored to him for mediation asked him to hold negotiations with their rivals and took advantage of his diplomatic skills as ambassador (Al-Mawardi, 2006). It reveals that he was not only a distinguished court justice and rather a great ambassador, and a practical administrator. He was also a distinguished authority and wrote mostly on law, politics ethics and administration and above all on political philosophy.

AL-MAWARDI'S WORKS

In the galaxy of the universal figures and thinkers al-Mawardi occupies a unique place. He was a prolific writer and composed at least fifteen books on various subjects including Quranic commentary, the tradition of the final prophet (SM).², jurisprudence, moral ethics, politics and the theories relating to the formation of state, constitutional problems, role of the Caliph, his duties, functions, his statesmanship particularly his role for, the socio-economic political development, appointment of the ministry and the administration of justice. He was-a great political economist, a great thinker and a philosopher who contributed his unique and original thought and theories in the realm of human knowledge and culture. His well-known works extant and treatises on law and political science are:

1. Kitab al-Hawi Wa-al-Iqna;
2. Adab al-Qawanin-al Wizirah
3. Facilitating Administration and Accelerating Victory. Tashil al-Nadhir Wa al-Ta'jil Al-Zafar
4. The Ordinances of Government Al-Ahkam-al-Sultaniyya

i) Kitab-al-Hawi wa-al-Iqna

² Here it is to be noted that when the name of our beloved Prophet Mohammad(sm) appears by a writing form or the uttering by tongue, we, all the while, have to recite *Sallallahu Alaihiwasallam*-as one of the traditions of the Prophet inspires us to do so without fail.

The condensed form of kitab-al-Hawi is entitled as al-Iqna written on Islamic law as Legal Epitome for the Hanafi'ties on the request of the Caliph al-Qadir (429/1037) which brought in him recognition as the best and in appreciation of his merit the Caliph appointed him as the Aqda al-Qudad- the supreme justice. The Shariah Law was one of his most favorite subjects in which he specialized and acquired a high degree of proficiency, particularly in *Furu* or doctrine of applied Fiqh of the Shafi'ite school. His penetrative and deep study on the principles and branches of Islamic jurisprudence has built him up -as one of the most learned jurists of his time. He excels all in his contemporaries and is regarded as one of the Imāms and Leaders of the Shafi'te School. About the book Al-Hawi al-Isravi conveys that no such book has ever been written on the subject [Shadharat-udh-Dhahab, 11, p. 285 quoted in the book of Qazi Akhter Ahmad Mian] (Mian, 1994).

ii) *Adab al-Qawanin-al Wizirah*

In his *Adab-al-Wizirah* al-Mawardi specifically deals with the definition and classification of Ministers, their duties and functions and particularly also the power, functions duties, and limitations of the prime minister. This treatise contains sound advice to ministers and lays down rules and practical suggestions which the ministers ought to follow while functioning as a head of the state in all affairs. It contains a concise survey of all that is worth knowing in any branch of Islamic culture (Mian, 1994).

iii) *Facilitating Administration and Accelerating Victory- The Tashil*

Al-Mawardi as a political theorist, indeed, developed latter on, his—*Facilitating Administration and Accelerating Victory-Tashil al-Nadher wa-Tajil al-Dhafar*. It was not meant or viewed to be a daily administrative manual for government official nor was it an attempt to justify current political emergency or to lend support to the Caliph in his struggle with the Buwahid Amirs. It was actually an attempt to formulate a politico-religious theory that focuses not only on how an Imam comes to power but on how political systems-in general-are instituted, maintained how and why decline, and how they are overthrown and replaced by others (Hamid, 2001) . It manifests him as a one of the greatest political philosopher in the discipline.

Here is to note that Professor Gibb and some other maintain that al-Mawardi set out to do was to describe the ideal state, a sort of Islamic counterpart to Plato's Republic or More's Utopia, but speculatively derived from the basic principles of Islam (Gibb, 1962). But Gibb stated subsequently that Al-Mawardi was not a philosopher and that legal speculation plays but a small part in his work (Gibb, 1962). Hamid Eltigani has clarified the fact that how Gibb missed matters relating to the true assessment of Al-Mawardi Eltigani shows that what al-Mawardi did not expose in his Ordinances-Ahkam, he rather freely evolved the political philosophy in his Tashil in detail which he has illustrated thus:

iv) The Ordinances of Government *Al-Ahkam*

It is told by some scholars that among all the works of al-Mawardi The Ordinances of Government *al-Ahkam-as-Sultaniyya* is by far the most important upon which his fame chiefly rest. It brings in him the great repute in his authorship in respect to endeavoring here his politics, administrative and constitutional theories. It must have written in the mid 5th hijri century and published in his life time in response both to the demand of the Abbasside Caliph and to the emerging political situation duly to cope with. Particularly, it was composed as an apology for the Abbasside caliph, who was facing many challenges and threats to his authority during the life time of al-Mawardi. Thus, this book also appeared as an attempt to assert the authority of the caliph and to show his legitimate superiority over the rising powers of his rivals as such the Buwaihids (amirs who were in actual control over the Abbasid State) (Rosenthal, 1962). His treatise can be regarded as one of the first scientific treatment in political science as well as in state administration (Sharif, 1963). Only a small portion of The Ordinances of Government- *Ahkam-as-Sultaniyya* is devoted to political theory, the rest of it discusses the details of public administration and role of government. But this small portion is extremely important because the first attempt in Islamic history to evolve a comprehensive theory of the state, and because it has left an enduring influence on the course of Muslim political thought upto our own day (Sharif, 1963). However, The Ordinances-*al-Ahkam* contains twenty chapters. The

first deal with contract for the Imamate, the second with ministerial appointment, the third with the appointment of provincial governors, the fourth with appointing war commanders, the fifth with appointing commanders of expedition in the public interest, the sixth with the Judicature, the seventh with appointment to the office of complains, the eight with the syndicate of the nobility, the ninth with prayer leaders, the tenth with leading the pilgrimage, the eleventh with the administration of zakah, the twelfth with the distribution of the spoils of war, the thirteenth with the tribute and the land tax, the fourteenth with distinctions among different provinces, the fifteenth with land reclamation and water supply, the sixteenth with enclosures and public amenities, the seventeenth with land grants and concessions, the eighteenth with the rules pertaining to the chancery, the nineteenth with crimes and the twentieth with the principles of the office of public morals and market supervision (Al-Mawardi, 2006).

THE THEORY OF IMAMAH OR KHILAFAH

The theory of Imamah is one of the permanent contribution of al-Mawardi that he propounded in his *-The Ordinances-Ahkam* becomes the main focus up to the time that the scholars have recognized. On the basis of the key principles of the Quranic verse³ (4:59), the traditions of the holy Prophet (sm.) and consensus. He formulated the theory of polity and its administration in detail. At the very beginning he puts forward the *raisen d'etre* of the polity that God has laid down laws for men. Moreover, God has entrusted the control of his creatures to various governments so that the administration of the world might be properly carried on. al-Mawardi adds that the Imamate, which literally means President-ship (in respect of presidential government) in modern phraseology, is the foundation on which the rules and regulations of the community depend on. These are solid truths and the more we consider the circumstances of the state and the government even today the more are we convinced of them (Sherwani, 1985). To put al-Mawardi's idea in modern

³. O ye who believe! Obey Allah, the Messenger and those of you who are in authority. (Quran: 4:59). And the Prophet (sm.) says, you will be ruled after me by some who are benign, and some who are depraved. Listen to them and obey them in all that is right. The good they do will be for your benefit and theirs; the bad they do will be for you and against them (Al-Mawardi, 2006).

form: what he means is *firstly*, that the real motive of the state is the rule of justice and truth, and *secondly* it is the machinery of the state which shifts the good from bad, virtue from vice, the sanctioned from the prohibited (Sherwani, 1985). As regards the essence of Imamate he asserts that the real motive of the institution is the following of the ‘straight path’ and the strengthening of political bonds, it is therefore of the utmost important that someone should be chosen Imam by the consensus of the community. Moreover, he says that the Imamate is not only an institution sanctioned by traditions and history but can be proved to the necessary according to pure reason, for wise man entrust their affairs to a leader able to keep them from being molested and to adjudge between them in case of mutual quarrels (Sherwani, 1985, p. 102). Even today, after the lapse of nearly a thousand years the state is a *sinequa non* of human society which exists to retain its true character for which it has been established. Here is to note that he shows a clear distinction between the government based on pure reason and the higher form of government based on revelation. The former, nearly guards against mutual injustice, strife, discord, and anarchy while the later provides for the positive enforcement of law and injustice in mutual confidence and friendship. Above all, the divinely revealed law enables the governor to administer religious affairs and prepare man for the world in the next.

Theory of Election

His theory of election of the appointment of an Imam is portrayed in *The Ordinances-Ahkam*-instead of regarding purely the artificial factors such as age, property and residence, he rather has stressed on the attributive and qualitative approach that only the qualified one who can distinguish between bad and good between right and wrong, between the deserving and the undeserving. The Electoral College shall consist of persons with the three attributes:

- i) Probity and justice in every sense of the world.
- ii) Knowledge leading to recognitions of the person fitted by his qualifications for the post of the supreme leader.

- iii)* Prudence and wisdom likely to make them choose the best candidate and the most capable and knowledgeable in managing state affairs (Al-Mawardi, 2006, p. 4).

To al-Mawardi, there are seven conditions of eligibility for the candidature of the supreme leadership: a) Justice or probity b) Knowledge c) Sound hearing, vision, and speech d) Physical fitness and freedom. e) Prudence f) Dauntless courage in defense g) Notable Qurayshite descent⁴

According to al-Mawardi the Caliph could be elected by one of the following methods:

- a. by nomination of the electoral colleges or
- b. by the process of nomination done by the existing Caliph

Succession by the nomination of a predecessor is permissible and correct by general consensus on the basis of two precedents adopted by Muslims and never put in dispute. The *first* is the appointment by Abu Bakr of Umar which was accepted by Muslims as sufficient to establish his leadership. The *second* is that Umar nominated for succession the counselors, being the select few, whose candidacy was accepted by the community (Al-Mawardi, 2006, p. 9). The Imam can nominate any suitable person as his successor, provided he does not happened to be his father or son. The concurrence of the *ahl al-hall wa al-aqd* is not necessary, but if he nominates his son, the concurrence must be obtained. Also he can nominate any other relation without requiring the concurrence (Sharif, 1963, p. 722). But in two methods the choices of a candidate for this office, to be valid, has to be confirmed by two steps: *first* by a private *baiyah*, that is investiture with the elector's oath of loyalty followed by the *second* step *bai'ah 'ammah*—confirmation in public to express national consensus *Ijma*, providing the newly elected Caliph with a contract investiture (*Ahd*) between him and the Muslim

⁴. Just after the death of the holy Prophet (sm.) the question of appointing a Caliph of the Prophet (sm.) appeared. When Medinan supporters (Ansars) gave their vote of allegiance to Sa'ad ibn Ubadah, (Umar and) Abu Bakr (R.) challenged their eligibility for the highest office of the Day of Saqifah citing the Prophet's (sm.) own words: Imam comes from Quraish, "Follow Quraysh and go not in advance of it." Accepting his statement and granting its authority they (Ansars) gave up all claims whether of an exclusive right to Caliphate or of the right to share it (Al-Mawardi, 2006, p. 4).

community (Rosenthal, 1962, p. 31). On referring to Ibn Qutaybah, Professor Qumaruddin has called this theory of the jurists unsupported by the traditions and the precedents of Islam thus:

The testimony of Ibn Qutaybah is most unequivocal and decisive. It completely abrogates al-Mawardi's theory of nomination. It is quite obvious that Abu Bakr did not deprive the people of their democratic right to elect the head of the state freely. He simply gave his personal opinion as well as rejected it. There was no political bar in their way, no caliphal decree to prevent the exercise of their franchise (Khan, 1959, pp. 64–65).

THE FUNCTIONS AND DUTIES OF THE IMAM

According to al-Mawardi the Imam has the following ten utmost duties to perform (Al-Mawardi, 2006, p. 16).

a) He must guard the faith, upholding its established sources and the consensus of the umma's ancestors. b) He must enforce law between disputing parties and end disagreement among antagonists until justice prevails and there are no more oppressors or oppressed people. c) He must protect the country and the household. d) He must dispense the legal punishments e) He must strengthen border posts by deterrent equipment and fighting force. f) He must fight those who resist the supremacy of Islam. g) He must collect the legal taxes and alms imposed by jurisprudence. h) He has to estimate the payments and allocation i) He must appoint men who are reliable and sincere j) He has personally to oversee matters and study the conditions of the people in order to manage public policy and guard the When the Imam has carried out all the duties efficiently, the people must offer him two things: obedience and help or support. The enumeration of the tenfold functions of the Imam is arbitrary. Number ten has been chosen particularly because it is an auspicious and mystical number. The notable fact here is that while his predecessors and successors lay great emphasis on the first two points meaning the safeguard of religious principles and the dispensation of justice, as the principle duties al-Mawardi being the practical jurist and Qazi al-Quzat lays the main stress on the administrative responsibility of the Caliph. In his opinion the Imamate or Caliphate is not merely a religious institution for the carrying out of justice but

also the greatest social organization to help promoting corporate life of men. In other words, the management of the state machinery is of basic importance to him. He explains why he devotes only one tenth of his book *Ahkam-The Ordinances* to the exposition of the theory of the Caliphate and uses the rest of his work to elaborate the detailed apparatus of government which hinges on the central authority of the Caliph (Sharif, 1963, pp. 727–728).

Rosenthal then concludes that the above tenfold functions to be rendered by the Caliph show quite the unity of religion and politics, of spiritual or temporary or religious and secular aspects of a life centered in and leading to God. The theory of Caliphate is modeled upon the primitive ‘Ummat al-Islam’ of Muhammad (sm.) in Medinah (Rosenthal, 1962, pp. 36–37).

IMPEACHMENT OF THE CALIPH

Then al-Mawardi has given a detailed consideration to the subject relating to impeachment of the Imām. *First* of all on arguing on the basis of legal deduction from the fundamental instructions of the Shariah he conveys that once a person is elected as Imām, he cannot be removed from that office until there has occurred a definite change in him. In accordance with his opinion the impeachment of an Imām from his post will happen only for the following reasons:

1. If there occurs a change in the moral status, technically known as *adalah* sense of justice which is of two kinds.
 - a. The one connected with his body that is, if he becomes a slave to his inordinate desire and flouts openly the prohibitions of the *shariah* in such an event a person can neither be elected as Imām nor continue as such.
 - b. The other connected with his faith that is if a person holds opinions contrary to the established principles of religion or holds such twisted opinions as amount to an abrogation of the accepted principles, he can neither be initiated as Imām nor continues to hold that office. In this there is a clear denunciation of the stand of the Buwaihids and of the Shi’ite and Fatimids claim to the Caliphate.
2. If there occurs a change in the person of the Imām in three folds:
 - a. Loss of physical senses

- b. Loss of bodily organs
- c. Loss of ability to supervise and direct the affairs of state.

Thus, Al-Mawardi gave a detailed account of the administrative machinery of the government of his time and formulating his political theory took full cognizance of historical facts.

Designation and Privileges

- i. When a person is duly elected as Imām, the people should entrust all their affairs to him and must give him their unquestioning obedience. The Imām may not consult them in the affairs of the state yet they must obey.
- ii. The Imām – may be addressed as Caliph of Rasulullah or in any proper term.

THE MINISTRY (WIZIRATE)

After dealing with the key institution of Imamah, al-Mawardi turns to the question of the Ministry-*wizirate*. At the outset of it he affirms that the appointment of a minister- *wazir* does not mean that the Imām or Caliph should give up all connections with the administration of the state but the real significance of his appointment consists in the fact that “in the province of politics it is better to have a co-adjutor rather than one sole person at the realm of affairs” (Al-Mawardi, 2006 chapter 2). It may be affirmed from the lesson of the Quran is that when the prophet Moses could make his brother Haron his wazir in order that his (Moses) hands should be strengthened. Therefore al-Mawardi thinks that in the administration of a state it is allowable for the Imam to have a wazir beside him. He, then, theorizes that the wazir is of two kinds, the Wizarate of delegation and the Wizarate of execution.

A. The Ministry-*Wizirah* of Delegation

The wizarate of delegation is the leading person in whom the Imān has the fullest confidence and to whom the whole administration of the realm is delegated. The sole differences between the wazir and the Imām himself is that the wazir of delegation cannot appoint any one as his successor, and the Imām can dismiss the officers appointed by him. In this regard, we see him to stress on the necessity of having a definite constitution of a state rightly being

affirmed from his own words: If the wazir gives a certain order and the Imām opposes it, then we should consider the essence of the order, if it is found that the order has been issued according to the dictation of the constitution then it should not be within the power of the Imām to rescind it (Al-Mawardi, 2006, p. 2). Now it would be fairly concluded that al-Mawardi was not ignorant of the nature of constitutional government even as we understand it in the modern terms.

B. The *Wizirah* of Execution:

The *wizirah* of execution is termed no other than the secretary to the government employed in modern state. Al-Mawardi illustrates that the key function of the wazir consists in executing the decrees of the main official channel of information for the Imam. Al-Mawardi has determined most required seven attributes for a person aspiring to the post of the wazir of execution such as honesty, confidence, absence of greed, good relationship with the people, intelligence and the power of grasping the truth of things, absence of luxury and finally diplomacy and experience. If the conditions are fulfilled, al-Mawardi opines then that it is not necessary that the holder of the office should be a follower of Islam, and a non-Muslim-The protected-*Dhimmi*, can also be appointed a *wazir* of the execution (Sherwani, 1985, p. 14).

THE JUDICIARY

Al-Mawadri has determined seven conditions as required for a judge:

- a) He should be a male sex (although according to Abu Hanifa a woman can also adjudicate, and Ibn Jarir agrees with him).
- b) He should be cleaver and intelligent
- c) He should be a free man
- d) He should be a Muslim (although Abu Hanifa is of opinion that even a non-Muslim may be appointed a judge).
- e) He should be honest, pious and above suspicious
- f) He should be well-versed in the principles of law and lastly
- g) He should not have any defect in his power of seeing and hearing in order that there should be no doubt left during the presentation of a case.

His being the chief justice (in the early Abbasid period, he knew the worth of the personality and significant role of a judge in dispensing justice. Therefore, he strongly and logically opined that it should be made absolutely certain whether a person is really possessed of these attributes either by previous knowledge or else by means of examination. He regards this office so sacred that when a man has been appointed a judge once he should neither be dismissed nor should he ordinarily resigned his post (Sherwani, 1985, p. 108). Establishment of justice mostly depends on the functioning of the judiciary of the government. It is the duty of the Imam or Caliph to ensure justice by his own strive and by the institution of the judiciary.

EPILOGUE

Al-Mawardi preceded many of the great political philosophers in the east and west even including Ibn Khaldun and others. On, relying on the Tashil al-Nadar' Hamid Eltigani tries his best to show in one of his entitlet, Al-Mawardi's Theory of State: some Ignored Dimensions that some of al-Maward's major ideas in political theory have not been seriously studied by any of the scholars including Professor Gibb, Ann Lambton, Professor Qumaruddin-M.M Sharif and others-who have written on Medieval Islamic Political Thought.

A close examination of al-Mawardi's works in general reveal that he is not mere a recorder of facts handed down to him by his predecessors but a genius statesman, a great diplomat, and outstanding jurist-mustahid the great theorist and a philosopher in true sense of the terms. It is observed that what al-Mawardi has put in the al-Ahkam does not constitute more than a small part of his political theory-a full exposition of which is delivered as a formulation of theory and philosophy in his *Tashil-an-Nadar- Facilitating Administration and Accelerating Victory*. Al-Mawadi is here more forthcoming and analytic than he appears to be in the Ahkam-The Ordinances . In the light of our re-reading of the two works, we can safely conclude that al-Ahkam-The Ordinances does not represent the final definite exposition of al-Mawardi's theory. Let alone the Aristotle or the Sunni political thought, as some scholars claimed. Had the *Tashil* been read seriously al-Mawardi would

not have remained seen as a mere Shafi'ite jurist who seeks, by way of deduction from theological premises to justify the legitimacy of the Abbasside rule. Indeed, the Tashil shows that al-Mawardi in neither attached to formal deduction as a political theorist, nor is he blindly attached as a political activist, to the Abbasid Caliphate. He bases his researches on a variety of sources the like of which is rarely met in other works (Hamidullah, 1983, p. 14). A part from Qur'anic verses and prophetic traditions, to which all jurists refer to it is amazing to know that al-Mawardi refers to 378 *hikma* (ancient saying of wise men), 114 verses from Arabic poetry, 14 quotations related to the prophetic companions; 13 quotations related to the companion's successors and proverbs. These other sources show how keen he is to incorporate human experience and make it a part of his epistemology and how keen he is to see the political phenomena as it really exists outside the text (Hamidullah, 1983).

The evolve and development of his political philosophy is directed to the aspects of the origin of state, instituting rule by force or power politics, money politics, the cyclical conception of state, the agricultural economy etc. which clearly determine of his being a great philosopher of Islam before both Ibn Khaldun and Ibn Taymiah.

His exposition of the political theory relating to Imamah and the philosophy of the origin of state, power politics, the cyclical conception of a state and economic development of state and nation in terms of the development of the agricultural economy and the analytical views in all these matters made him a philosopher indeed and finally he could rightly be regarded as the predecessor of both Ibn Khaldun and Ibn Taymiah. Three centuries prior to Ibn Khaldun al-Mawardi wrote intensively about these very ideas that Ibn Khaldun undeniably, reproduce in a better form. Seeing that some of al-Mawardi's idea have been blurred by way of exaggerating Ibn Khaldun's originality, again, it is Professor Gibb who has brought a passage from Ibn Taymiah's work (d. 728/1328) if that passage is compared with the introduction to book 1, section 1, of the Muqaddima, or such a statement as book iii, chapter 23, or the still more illuminating in book 5, chapter 6, will be seen that Ibn Khaldun does little more than these ideas and gave them greater

precision by introducing his conception of *Asabiyyah*. It should be mentioned here that Ibn Khaldun refers to al-Mawardi's *Ahkam-The Ordinances* explicitly in many a places in his *Muqaddima* (Khaldun, 1958). Notwithstanding the significant comparison and valid argument, Gibb himself has not gone through far beyond Ibn Taymiyyah and al-Mawardi's *Ahkam-The Ordinances*, had he done so he might have seen clearly that both Ibn Khaldun and Ibn Taymiyyah have relied intensively on al-Mawardi's *Tashil* and they have done little more that put his condensed ideas in longer and expounded statements. The final view of us relating to the intellectual capacity of al-Mawardi is established that he was not mere a recorder of facts handed down to him from his predecessors, but, a diplomat, a capable administrator and outstanding jurist, a genius statesman of all times, and the chief justice-the Qadi al-Qudat in the Abbasside empire. Really he was a great theorist and a philosopher in its true sense that he appeared as one of the world political philosophers that the Muslim world produced in the middle age during Abbasside period. Along with other things his greatness lies in the jurist's transformation of the past and the preset into a coherent logical system that has popularized it generation after generation (Bhat, 1996, p. 33).

REFERENCES

- Al-Mawardi. (2006). *The Ordinance of Government-al-Ahkam al-Sultaniyyah W'al Wilayat Al Dinniyya*. Garnet Publishing.
- Bhat, A. R. (1996). *Political Thought of Shah Waliullah*. Adam publishers and Distributors.
- Gibb, H. A. (1962). *Studies in Islamic Civilization*. Routledge.
- Hamid, E. A. Q. (2001). Al-Mawardi's Theory of a State: Some Ignored Dimensions. *American Journal of Social Sciences*, 18(4).
- Hamidullah, M. (1983). *The Emergence of Islam: Lectures on the Development of Islamic World-view, Intellectual Tradition and Polity* (A. Iqbal (ed.)). Islamic Research Institute in collaboration with Da'wah Academy, International Islamic University.
- Khaldun, I. (1958). *The Muqaddimah*. Routledge and Cegan Paul.
- Khan, Q.-D. (1959). *Al-Mawardi's Theory of the State* (1st ed.). University of Michigan.

- Lambton, A. K. S. (1981). *State and Government in Medieval Islam*. Oxford University Press.
- Mian, Q. A. A. (1994). *Al-Mawardi: A Sketch of His Life and Works in Islamic Culture*.
- Rosenthal, E. I. J. (1962). *Political Thought in Medieval Islam: An Introductory Outline* (Reissue ed). Cambridge University Press (CUP Archive, 1962).
- Sharif, M. M. (1963). *A History of Muslim Philosophy With short accounts of other Disciplines and the Modern Renaissance in the Muslim Lands* (1st ed., Vol. 1). Royal Book Company.
- Sherwani, H. K. (1985). *Studies in Muslim Political Thought And Administration* (S. M. Ashraf (ed.); 2nd ed.). Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers Pvt Ltd. <https://www.amazon.com/Muslim-Political-Thought-Administration-Sherwani/dp/8121501962>

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EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH: PERSPECTIVES FROM LEARNERS AND TEACHERS OF ENGLISH VERSION SCHOOLS

ALIA RAWSHAN BANU¹

ABSTRACT

The objective of introducing English Version schools in Bangla medium schools is government's concern on the nation's human capital development. To achieve the standard of a developed country, both national and foreign curricula are implemented in the educational sector in Bangladesh. This paper emphasizes the difficulties that English language learners face in comprehending the language since EV schools do not provide enough opportunity for real-world experience and reflective activities. This research seeks to examine the challenges that students have while utilizing and comprehending English vocabulary and phrases in the context of their coursework. A qualitative data analysis approach was used to capture the

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thoughts and opinions of ten students from class X in five different English Version schools. The findings of this survey reveal the participants' attitudes, opinions, and interests on the difficulties, issues, and prospects of English-language institutions. While these schools adhere to the national curriculum, they mostly use English as the medium of teaching. Furthermore, this research has significant pedagogical implications for individuals learning the English language, as well as for instructors and professionals in the field.

Keywords: English Version Institution in Bangladesh, National Curriculum, English Moi

INTRODUCTION

To learn the language effectively, our textbooks used in schools and colleges are designed following National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB) prescribed curriculum. Under the Ministry of Education in Bangladesh, education system has been divided into two sections: the traditional 'Bengali medium' schools and the 'English version'. However, there is perhaps a discrimination between the different education systems when it comes to the practice of all necessary skills needed to perform well in English. English as a lingua franca is used almost everywhere around the globe as a mode of communication and contact with people for different purposes. So, English is taught and learnt as foreign or second language for communication, higher study and getting a good job etc. In Bangladesh, English is taught as foreign language and is considered as compulsory from primary to tertiary education (Moni, 2021; NCTB, 2021; Taz, 2021).

The objective for introducing English Version Schools in Bangla medium schools is government's concern on the nation's human capital development in order to achieve the standard of a developed country, as well as an early preparation to compete in the era of globalization. However, this study aims to explore the challenges among the secondary students studying in English Version Institution in our country (Taz, 2021).

Background of the Study

English version schools in Bangladesh provide an educational framework combining the national curriculum with English as the language of teaching.

These institutions are kept under the framework of the national curriculum but serve students who want a greater exposure to global education standards.

Over the last ten years, English version schools in Bangladesh have been progressively growing in count. According to statistics of 2022, there are several hundred schools have English version all throughout the nation, mostly concentrated in cities like Dhaka, Chittagong, and Sylhet. Although exact figures vary, under different educational boards there are approximately 2.2% English versions of institutions all around (BANBEIS, 2022).

English version schools usually provide instruction beginning in Class 1 (Grade 1) and running through Class 12 (Grade 12). From Class 1 to Class 5, the education starts at the elementary level; it then proceeds through the junior secondary level from Class 6 to Class 8; the secondary level from Class 9 to Class 10; and ends at the upper secondary level from Class 11 to Class 12. To equip children for the main level, certain schools could also provide pre-primary education (NCTB, 2021).

Although the English version of the National Curriculum, Textbook Board (NCTB) of Bangladesh provides the textbooks used, the curriculum in English version schools is compliant with the national curriculum. With the main distinction being the method of education, these textbooks cover all disciplines—including Bangla, English, mathematics, science, social science, and others. The material stays the same, just as in the Bangla edition textbooks, thereby guaranteeing students's readiness for national tests (NCTB, 2021; Taz, 2021).

English version schools welcome students from all backgrounds. Though admissions may sometimes occur at higher levels depending on the availability of seats and the school's policies, generally students are accepted at the entry-level, Class 1. Usually, admission calls for passing an entrance test—especially for higher grades. Usually keeping to the national curriculum, the schools serve moderate to upper-middle class learners who want an English-medium education (NCTB, 2021).

Research Problem

English is used worldwide and has been popular for a few centuries which results in different varieties of English. People across the world are getting habituated with these diversities. In our country, despite using English in almost all sectors, we face controversies over non-native norms, standards, practices and attitudes. Both national and foreign curricula are implemented in the educational sector in Bangladesh. This research seeks to examine the challenges that students have while utilizing and comprehending English vocabulary and phrases in the context of their coursework.

Learning does not happen by only passive receipt of information (Chand, 2023). In the context of the challenges faced by learners and teachers in English Version schools, constructivist theory provides a robust framework for understanding these issues. The research problem could be framed as exploring how the lack of authentic, experiential learning opportunities and reflective practices in EV schools contributes to the challenges learners face in constructing their understanding of English.

Additionally, it may also address how instructors could find it difficult to use constructivist techniques in a system that does not entirely support these methods, therefore creating a gap between theory and practice. Through constructivist theory, the research might provide insights on how English language instruction in EV schools could be strengthened to better fit the ideas of active, experiential, and socially constructed learning.

CONSTRUCTIVIST THEORY AND ITS APPLICATION TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

Constructivist Theory Overview

Psychologists like Jean Piaget (D. 1980) and Lev Vygotsky (D. 1934) were constructivists. Their theory claims that learning is an active and creative process. By use of experiences, connections, and reflection, learners create or develop their own understanding and knowledge of the world. Learning does not happen by only passive receipt of information. This strategy goes against

the view that learners are blank slates; they wait for the teachers to load with knowledge (Access & Sardar, 2023; Chand, 2023).

Constructivism holds that learning is a process of meaning construction from experience. Not just handed on from teacher to student, knowledge is actively formed by the learner when they mix new content with their present cognitive structures. This method that information is created is much shaped by the social and cultural environment in which education takes place (Chand, 2023).

Major Proponents of this Theory

Jean Piaget: Piaget introduced the concept of cognitive constructivism. It suggests that learners build their own knowledge through processes of assimilation and accommodation of their experiences. Piaget emphasized the importance of active engagement in learning, where learners interact with the world around them and construct new meaning (Liu & Matthews, 2005).

Lev Vygotsky: Later, Vygotsky expanded on Piaget's theory of learning with his sociocultural theory. Vygotsky underscores the importance of social interaction and cultural tools in the learning process. He introduced the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which is the difference between what a learner can do without help and what they can achieve with guidance and encouragement from a skilled partner. This idea highlights the role of teachers, peers, and social context in the construction of knowledge (Access & Sardar, 2023).

Jerome Bruner: Bruner (D. 2016) further developed the constructivist approach by emphasizing the role of language and narrative in learning. He argued that learning is an active process where learners construct new ideas based on their current and past knowledge. Bruner also highlighted the importance of scaffolding, where teachers support learners by providing temporary structures to help them achieve higher levels of understanding (O'donovan, 2021).

Application to English Language Learning

Above theories of cognitive constructivism, socio cultural theory and scaffolding can be applied very well in English language acquisition of EV schools. Constructivist theory suggests that learners acquire language skills most effectively through authentic, meaningful experiences that allow them to engage with the language in context. This means that learners construct their understanding of English not merely by memorizing vocabulary or grammar rules, but by using the language in real-life situations, reflecting on their usage, and gradually internalizing the language structures.

Several key ideas emerge from this constructivist approach to language learning:

Learning through Experience: English language learners benefit from immersive experiences where they can use the language in meaningful ways. For example, activities like role-playing, simulations, and project-based learning allow students to construct their understanding of English. By doing so, they can apply English to real-world scenarios (Access & Sardar, 2023; Kilpatrick, 1953).

Reflection: Reflective practice is crucial in language learning. After engaging in language use, learners reflect on their experiences, analyze their language output, and adjust. This reflective process helps them internalize language rules and structures. This is how their learning becomes more effective (Ha, 2022).

Social Interaction: Vygotsky's emphasis on social interaction is particularly relevant in language learning. Classroom conversations, collaborative tasks, and peer feedback sessions allow learners to construct their knowledge of English. Learners need to learn from others and receive support in social contexts (Lantolf et al., 2014; Marks & Fraley, 2007).

Cultural Context: Learning a language within a cultural context is also important. Language is deeply intertwined with culture. Understanding the cultural context and pragmatics of English is crucial for learners and teachers. This means that language learning should not be isolated from the

cultural contexts in which the language is used (Karlik, 2023; Ordóñez Procel et al., 2023).

Constructivist Perspectives on Learning English

Several scholars have specifically applied constructivist principles to language learning:

David Ausubel emphasized the role of prior knowledge in learning new concepts, which is crucial in language learning. He suggested that learners anchor new language concepts to what they already know, which helps in better retention and understanding (“Learning Theories: Ausubel’s Learning Theory,” 2012).

John Dewey, a proponent of experiential learning, argued that education should be grounded in real-life experiences. In the context of learning English, this means that students learn best when they can relate language lessons to their personal experiences and use the language in practical, everyday situations (Kilpatrick, 1953; Roberts, 2003).

Krashen’s Input Hypothesis aligns with constructivist ideas, proposing that language acquisition occurs when learners are exposed to language input that is slightly above their current level of competence ($i+1$). This challenges learners to construct meaning and advance their language skills (Senturk, 2024).

The Present Study

In this study, the researcher attempts to analyse the ongoing developmental endeavour of Bangladeshi education system, namely, English version sections in Bangla medium schools of Bangladesh. Although a remarkable number of Bangladeshi schools has involved themselves in this attempt of immersion education, there is still inadequate amount of research on benefits and losses of the project ‘English version’ taken by Bangladesh Govt. This paper discloses the challenges, thoughts and actions taken by the students of English Version Institutions of Bangladesh. This paper answers the following research questions:

1. What are the challenges the students as well as teachers face in English Version classroom?
2. What strategies do they use to address the challenges experienced in an English-language classroom?

LITERATURE REVIEW

History and Definition of English Version

In 1960s, Bangladesh (the then East Pakistan) became familiar with the names as “English-teaching school” (Banu, R., & Sussex, 1999) and “National curriculum in English medium” (Al-Quaderi, G. G., & Al Mahmud, 2010), which came into use across West and East Pakistan (today’s Bangladesh) in response to public demand (Hasan, 2011).

English Version section follows national “Bangladesh Textbook Board Curriculum” but utilizes English as the medium of instruction (Rahman & Pandian, 2018) and under this name, this section has been perceived and employed all over the country as a compromise between desirable (higher) standards of international (English-medium) schools and affordable (but lower) standards of Bangla-medium schools (Moni, 2021; Rahman & Pandian, 2018).

The use of English as the primary language of teaching throughout the foundational stages of school, known as immersion education, is being critically examined by researchers. The references used are (Bialystok, 2012) and (Caccavale, 2007). UNESCO supports vernacular education as the most appropriate method of teaching all topics and recommends mother-tongue-based multilingual education to accomplish the objectives of “Education for All” (Lor, 2007).

Clear and intelligible communication is crucial for successful education, making the language of instruction vital to the learning process. Mother tongue-based teaching is essential for giving children early access to education and allowing them to engage in learning based on their developing abilities (Unesco, 2011).

Nevertheless, the current prevalence of utilizing English in Bangladeshi institutions indicates that there are various obstacles that need sufficient attention. It is critical to prioritize classroom-based assessment and integrate it into the overall assessment system, since the classroom plays a vital role in facilitating effective learning in an English language environment, such as in Bangladesh (Moni, 2021).

Present State of English Version in Bangladesh

Developing nations, such as Bangladesh, often have a common practice of making English a mandatory subject in formal education from the very beginning, even if there is a lack of competent instructors. An extensive analysis of many publications on education systems in different Least Developed Countries (LDCs) highlights notable features of the English version portion in Bangladesh. Primarily, the objective is to provide high-quality education aligned with the national curriculum. Furthermore, parents like the use of English as the primary language of teaching due to its effectiveness in facilitating knowledge of both curricular material and the English language. Furthermore, a significant portion of students have a middle-income social position, despite the fact that many of them face financial difficulties while trying to satisfy their basic needs with an average pay. Lastly, these schools are considered to be quasi-English-medium, which means that code-switching in the classroom is a common occurrence for both instructors and students (Rahman et al., 2019).

In Bangladesh, the English Version of education requires learners to comprehend the subject content in English, and it necessitates instructors with sufficient English competence who are willing to work for a little price. This presents a chance for young and driven teams of instructors who are receptive to innovative technology, methodologies, and teacher-student interactions (Golam & Tatsuya, 2019).

Challenges of Learning English as Second Language

In a constrained educational setting, learning materials are essential objects or resources that assist in the process of acquiring knowledge or skills. While

books are indeed crucial, they are insufficient on their own. Additionally, audio tools are required. Regrettably, students of the English language are never exposed to accurate pronunciation by a native speaker. Consequently, the majority of language acquisition is flawed. Students possess books for reading, but they lack knowledge about the accurate pronunciation of certain terms. Therefore, how can a learner acquire knowledge of word pronunciation? The student should be given the chance to receive proper pronunciation guidance from their instructor. Learning a second language primarily involves acquiring the ability to speak and understand it. However, learners cannot achieve a high degree of expertise unless they possess the ability to use the target language effectively within the framework of the target culture. Moreover, to acquire a practical and comprehensive understanding of language, learners must possess the ability to accurately infer the intended meaning of their conversation partners. When the L1 and L2 cultures exhibit common characteristics, the assumptions made play a role in the learning process. Nevertheless, when there are significant differences between both cultures, the process of learning becomes jeopardized (Raju & Joshith, 2017).

In comparison between spoken and written English, acquiring fluency in a foreign language is comparatively simpler than mastering its written form, grammatical rules, and the skill of writing it. It is thus unsurprising that Indians excel at spoken English compared to written English (Neha, 2019).

Common expressions and dialects also present challenges. This issue arises from the usage of informal language, namely slang, which is frequently employed in everyday interactions. By immersing yourself in the local culture, you will increase your opportunities to learn and adapt. Therefore, one may use popular culture such as television shows or radio programs to enable the student to discern indicators such as vocal intonation or nonverbal signals (Usman, 2019).

In addition, inexperienced instructors present another significant challenge. The majority of instructors lack knowledge on how to effectively introduce a new language to students based on their individual interests. Teachers sometimes struggle to effectively convey the aspects of a second

language, particularly when they themselves come from a different academic background and are teaching English in the classroom. In our secondary classrooms, the English instructors do not have a background in English as a subject. This consistently generates issues among learners. Notably, rural kids had a greater awareness of the impact of ‘Attitude’ and ‘Teacher’s Competence’ on their difficulties in learning English as a Second Language compared to urban learners (Raja & Selvi, 2011).

Further, restricted competence among instructors is another issue. Regrettably, the majority of high school instructors lack proficiency in the English language and are incapable of delivering oral instruction in English. Consequently, English is taught to learners mostly via written language, although this method does not guarantee complete mastery of the language. The most effective method of English instruction is oral language teaching in the classroom. It provides an opportunity for learners to listen to the target language. Consequently, the student will be required to communicate in English, which will enhance their ability to acquire the language (Raju & Joshith, 2017).

Finally, the absence of motivation significantly hampers language learning. Cook (Mahadi & Jafari, 2012) noted that language acquisition differs across learners and emphasized three key aspects that affect and impact the process of learning a second language. The three factors that influence this are age, personality, and motivation. Additionally, he asserts that motivation is the primary determinant in the acquisition of a second language. According to Betal & Banerjee (1996), motivation in second language acquisition is a multifaceted concept that may be described by two factors: the learners’ desire to communicate and their views towards the second language community. They hold the belief that when learners see the necessity of speaking a second language to connect with people or achieve certain objectives, they will be motivated and encouraged to acquire proficiency and mastery in it. This aligns with (R. Ellis, 1994) perspective, which defines motivation as learners’ deliberate effort to acquire a second language due to their inherent need or strong inclination to do so.

Finding Learners' Motivation

Engaging instructional methods in the classroom are crucial for maintaining student motivation and fostering their comprehension of teachings, as well as developing their expressive skills (Ariatna, 2016). Learners' motivation originates inside, but it is also necessary for the instructor to boost it in the classroom.

According to BANBEIS, there is a progressive increase in both the number and quality of teaching experts. The inclusion of English version parts significantly enhances children's comprehension of the topics and improves their proficiency in the English language. Most likely, this is because families, teachers, and the whole society see it as beneficial for learners to acquire proficiency in a second language, enabling them to become bilingual and bi-literate.

Context of English Version Classroom

English is a compulsory language for communication and teaching at English Version Institutions, even when the students and professors lack fluency in English. English is a mandatory subject and when it comes to teaching English, (Shahzada, G., Ghazi, S. R., & Khan, 2012) argue that the adoption of the Grammar Translation technique hinders students' progress in learning the language. Additionally, they assert that the schools do not prioritize the teaching and practice of communicative English, instead placing greater emphasis on teaching English texts. In addition, (Farooqui, 2014) asserts that the inadequate English competence of both instructors and learners leads to the use of Bengali for classroom instructions (Ali & Walker, 2014).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This section provides a comprehensive description of the research technique, including all the necessary components for doing the study. The objective of the research is to analyze the challenges and obstacles that students of the English Version Institution encounter in comprehending the subject matter specified by NCTB. A study design serves as a structured plan for gathering and analyzing data (Bryman, 2012). This study was conducted using a

qualitative research technique, where data was gathered via interviews and observations.

Participants

The participants have been taken from Secondary School of English Version Institution. The study has been conducted on 10 participants from Class X. This study adopts a qualitative multiple case study method that focuses on the actual information collected from the participants' interview.

Participants' Profile

Sl.	Name	Gender	Class	Name of the Institution
1.	Afifa	Female	X	Secondary school
2.	Rubel	Male	X	Secondary school
3.	Rebeca	Female	X	Secondary school
4.	Sajjad	Male	X	Secondary school
5.	Tamim	Male	X	Secondary school
6.	Farhan	Male	X	Secondary school
7.	Tanjim	Female	X	Secondary school
8.	Selina	Female	X	Secondary school
9.	Rokhsana	Female	X	Secondary school
10.	Momtaz	Female	X	Secondary school

Data Collection

Individual participants were interviewed, and data were also obtained via classroom observation. During the interview, the researcher sought to ascertain the difficulties encountered by students learning in the English Version. During the interview, the questions were posed in a candid and relaxed manner, allowing the participants to feel at ease in providing their answers. By following this approach, it is feasible to get genuine data. During the interviews, both Bengali and English were used to create a comfortable and informal atmosphere for the participants. This approach aimed to maximize the amount of information extracted while minimizing the chances of the participants losing interest towards the conclusion of the interview. The

interviews were taped and transcribed for the purpose of analysis and citation of the findings. Upon analyzing the responses to the interview questions, we will identify the primary challenges that students of the English Version Institution often encounter in our nation.

Data Analysis

The researcher has opted to use the qualitative thematic analysis framework (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017) to assemble and analyze the data gathered in this study. The data obtained from the interviews were examined using the researcher's hypothesis and corroborated by current studies examined in the literature.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher guarantees meticulous adherence to ethical considerations while performing the study and gathering data. Participants were not compelled to provide interviews or respond in a pre-determined manner. Furthermore, in order to safeguard privacy, pseudonyms are used for the participants and the names of the schools are completely omitted.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This research seeks to examine the difficulties faced by both students and instructors at English medium institutions while studying texts and comprehending the lesson's message. This section primarily aims to examine and evaluate the perspectives of the participants, using data obtained from interviews and the researcher's observations. This also includes the researcher's own perspective and potential resolutions to the issue.

Facing Difficulties in Understanding English Version Textbooks

It is really challenging to teach and study using a foreign language in a school atmosphere that is not very effective (Galloway et al., 2017). The primary grievances expressed by parents and learners are the inadequate proficiency of instructors in English, ineffective teaching methods, and the low quality of teaching materials. Following a discussion on preliminary inquiries, the researcher inquired about the educational setting at English Version institutions. During the interview, Tamim said that he has embarrassment

while encountering new topics and concepts when studying scientific courses in English Version textbooks (Nur, 2021)

In addition, while he posed pertinent inquiries to the instructors, the majority of the time, the teacher responded by stating that they will address it at a later time, leaving the issue unresolved. Conversely, several instructors argue that the learners are mischievous and that, despite their efforts to be helpful and kind, they are unable to effectively manage the situation.

Another participant, Rebeca, asserts that the authoritative position of a teacher instills fear in us, hindering our ability to ask questions and thereby diminishing opportunities for student-teacher interactions. Furthermore, Farhan, Tanjim, Selina, and other students and instructors assert that the comprehension of English textbooks is contingent upon the students' cognitive capacity. The variation is individual-specific.

Weak and not Interested in Bangla Subject

In English Version institutions, as the mode of communication and instruction is English, students are not interested to learn Bangla. Most of the students said, "Bangla classes are not so impressive as other classes". Moreover, Afifa, Rebeca, Rubel, Tamim asserts that from the very beginning of their student life, they did not give emphasis on Bangla as a compulsory subject and showed reluctance to study Bangla. For this, they always obtain poor marks in Bangla and find it difficult to learn Bangla despite Bangla as their mother tongue (Nur, 2021). So it is proved that English Version students face challenges to study Bangla and as a result, they don't feel interest in Bangla and in most cases they become reluctant to learn Bangla as a subject.

Use of Bangla Version Textbooks for Better Understanding

Based on the participants' feedback, it can be concluded that the English proficiency level of Bangladeshi students is very poor. The proficiency of English language in Bangla medium schools in Bangladesh is low due to the socio-economic status of the sector. English medium schools, on the other hand, are only accessible to the privileged classes (Hamid & Erling, 2014). Afifa states that when faced with vocabulary shortages, she employs several

strategies to overcome the difficulties. She sometimes looks up unfamiliar terms in the dictionary and other times seeks assistance from her instructor.

Nevertheless, when the researcher inquires about the use of Bangla textbooks to enhance their comprehension of the subject matter. Tamim, Rokhsana, and Tanjim acknowledge that they use Bangla textbooks when necessary. However, the decision is contingent upon the students' and instructors' level of competence. Furthermore, it is important for professors to assist learners in overcoming their apprehension towards comprehending English-language classes right from the outset of their academic journey.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This research primarily examines the difficulties encountered by instructors and students in the English Version Sections of Bengali medium schools, where children are taught using English as the medium of instruction, following the National Curriculum of Bangladesh. The researcher discloses that learners studying in the English Version have deficiencies and are deficient in Bangla owing to their unwillingness and lack of enthusiasm in this topic. In addition, their proficiency in English language is lacking and they do not prioritize the importance of writing sentences accurately.

Nowadays English is widely acknowledged for the development of a country as the vast majority of scientific studies, inventions, national and international interactions, business relations and corporate meetings are in the English language. So, the researcher strongly recommends the implementation of English Version Sections to contribute to students' academic achievement.

In conclusion, this paper found the dual challenges faced by students in English Version sections—insufficient proficiency in both Bangla and English. Despite the aim to enhance bilingual competence among learners, the current approach may fall short in achieving balanced language mastery. To address these issues, a more integrated and supportive learning environment is needed, where both languages are given equal emphasis and students are encouraged to value their cultural and linguistic heritage.

Recommendations:

1. **Enhanced Teacher Training:** To provide targeted professional development for teachers to better equip them with the skills needed to teach both Bangla and English effectively.
2. **Regular Assessments:** To implement regular assessments to monitor students' progress in both languages, allowing for timely interventions to address any deficiencies and to support students' holistic language development. These steps will not only enhance language proficiency but also ensure that students in English Version sections are well-prepared to meet the demands of the modern, globalized world.
3. **Learners' Motivation:** To encourage the learners to be motivated in comprehending a foreign language so that they can be able to understand and use it properly and effectively. Because motivation plays a vital role in the teaching and learning environment.

REFERENCES

- Access, O., & Sardar, A. (2023). Constructivism in Education: A Comprehensive Review of Theory and Research. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 07. <https://doi.org/10.56726/irjmets43553>
- Al-Quaderi, G. G., & Al Mahmud, A. (2010). English literature in English medium schools in Bangladesh: The question of post-colonial pedagogy. *Asiatic*.
- Ali, M., & Walker, A. L. (2014). Boggled down ELT in Bangladesh: Problems and policy. *English Today*, 30(2), 33–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266078414000108>
- Ariatna. (2016). The Need for Maintaining CLT in Indonesia. *TESOL Journal*, 7(4).
- BANBEIS. (2022). Bangladesh Education Statistics. Chapter- Eight University Education. Number of University,8.1. *Bangladesh Education Statistics*, April, 1–17. <http://data.banbeis.gov.bd/>
- Banu, R., & Sussex, R. (1999). English in Bangladesh after independence: Dynamics of policy and practice. *Oxford University Press*.
- Betal, A. K., & Banerjee, J. (1996). Factors Affecting Setswana-Speaking Children's Acquisition of English as a Second Language. *Tydskrif Vir Taalonderrig/Journal for Language Teaching*, 30(2), 111–123.
- Bialystok, E. et al. (2012). Linguistic and metalinguistic outcomes of intense immersion education: how bilingual? *Baycrest*.

- <http://research.baycrest.org/publication/view/id/13679>
- Bryman, A. (2012). *Social research methods* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Caccavale, T. (2007). The Correlation between Early Second Language Learning and Native Language Skill Development. *Learning Languages*.
- Chand, S. P. (2023). Constructivism in Education: Exploring the Contributions of Piaget, Vygotsky, and Bruner. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 12(7), 274–278. <https://doi.org/10.21275/sr23630021800>
- Farooqui, S. (2014). The struggle to teach in English: A case study in Bangladesh. *Journal of Education and Human Development*, 3(2), 441–457.
- Galloway, N., Kriukow, J., & Numajiri, T. (2017). Internationalisation, higher education and the growing demand for English: an investigation into the English medium of instruction (EMI) movement in China and Japan. In *British Council ELT Research Papers* (Vol. 17, Issue 2). [https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/sites/teacheng/files/H035_ELTRA Internationalisation_HE_and the growing demand for English A4_FINAL_WEB.pdf](https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/sites/teacheng/files/H035_ELTRA_Internationalisation_HE_and_the_growing_demand_for_English_A4_FINAL_WEB.pdf)
- Golam, A. M., & Tatsuya, K. (2019). Can we Formulate English Education Policies Which Respond to Ground Level? Comparative Study between Sub-urban & Remote Rural Areas in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal Of Administration and Management*, 28.
- Ha, N. T. H. (2022). An Exploratory Study On Reflective Practice Of L2 Experiences In An Ma Tesol. In *British Council's Master's Dissertation Awards 2023 Commendation*. University of Warwick.
- Hamid, M. O., & Erling, E. J. (2014). English-in-Education Policy and Planning in Bangladesh: A Critical Examination. *English Language Education Policy in Asia*, 9(November), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-22464-0>
- Hasan, O. (2011). *Education in transition: English based learning in Bangladesh today*. The Daily Star. <http://www.thedailystar.net/news-detail-196540>
- Karlik, M. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Culture on Language Learning: How Understanding Cultural Context and Values Can Deepen Language Acquisition. *International Journal of Language, Linguistics, Literature and Culture*, 02(05), 05–11. <https://doi.org/10.59009/ijlllc.2023.0035>
- Kilpatrick, W. H. (1953). Dewey's Philosophy of Education. *Educational Forum*, 17(2), 143–154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131725309341597>
- Lantolf, J. P., Thorne, S. L., & Poehner, M. E. (2014). Sociocultural theory and second language development. In *Theories in Second Language Acquisition: An Introduction* (Vol. 4415).

- <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203628942-16>
- Learning Theories: Ausubel's Learning Theory. (2012). In *University of Pendidikan Indonesia*.
http://fpmipa.upi.edu/data/report_activity/9875881844.pdf
- Liu, C. H., & Matthews, R. (2005). Vygotsky's philosophy: Constructivism and its criticisms examined. *International Education Journal*, 6(3), 386–399.
- Lor, P. J. (2007). The 34th General Conference of UNESCO. *IFLA Journal*, 33(4), 363–373. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0340035207087728>
- Maguire, M., & Delahunt, B. (2017). Doing a Thematic Analysis: A Practical, Step-by-Step Guide for Learning and Teaching Scholars. *Dundalk Institute of Technology*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.2014.2306979>
- Mahadi, D. T. S. T., & Jafari, S. M. (2012). Motivation, Its Types, and Its Impacts in Language Learning. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 50(1 PART 3), 230–235. <https://doi.org/10.1143/JJAP.50.01BC04>
- Marks, M. J., & Fraley, R. C. (2007). The impact of social interaction on the sexual double standard. *Social Influence*, 2(1), 29–54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15534510601154413>
- Moni, R. (2021). *Comparison between Bengali and English Medium Schools' Language Teaching Materials: A Secondary Level Study*. BRAC University.
- NCTB. (2021). National Curriculum and Textbook Board, Bangladesh National Curriculum Framework 2021 Pre-Primary to Grade 12. *National Curriculum and Textbook Board*. https://nctb.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/nctb.portal.gov.bd/page/0d5a8524_e5bc_4bfc_9e14_985380773fa9/2023-04-05-05-53-eb730ced57e4704a4e10e83b40a6d305.pdf
- Neha, D. (2019). Challenges of Learning English As a Second Language. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 01(5), 1–23.
- Nur, N. (2021). *The Challenges Of Learning Bangla In English Nuvia* (Issue February). Brac University February.
- O'donovan, M. (2021). *An Overview Of Bruner and Piaget-Cognitive Constructivists*. 1–31.
- Ordóñez Procel, G. J., Poma Tacuri, M. A., López López, K. A., & Correa Criollo, P. I. (2023). The Influence of Cultural Context on English Teaching. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, 7(4), 784–800. https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v7i4.6920
- R. Ellis. (1994). *The Study of Second Language Acquisition*. 53–55.
- Rahman, M. M., Islam, M. S., Karim, A., Chowdhury, T. A., Rahman, M. M., Seraj, P. M. I., & Singh, M. K. M. (2019). English language teaching in Bangladesh today: Issues, outcomes and implications. *Language Testing in Asia*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-019-0085-8>

- Rahman, M. M., & Pandian, A. (2018). A critical investigation of English language teaching in Bangladesh. *English Today*, 34(3), 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S026607841700061X>
- Raja, B. W. D., & Selvi, K. (2011). Causes of Problems in Learning English as A Second Language as Perceived by Higher Secondary Students. *I-Manager's Journal on English Language Teaching*, 1(4), 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.26634/jelt.1.4.1604>
- Raju, N., & Joshith, V. . (2017). Adversities and obstacles in learning English as a second language in Indian context. *International Journal of Advanced Education and Research*, 2(4), 48–51.
- Roberts, G. T. (2003). An Interpretation Of Dewey's Experiential Learning Theory. *Opinions Papers*, 10.
- Senturk, S. (2024). *Language Acquisition And Literature : Comprehensible Input In Classes*. February.
- Shahzada, G., Ghazi, S. R., & Khan, U. A. (2012). Causes of rising failure of the students' in The subject of English at Secondary Level. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1).
- Taz, S. (2021). English Version In Bangladesh : The Awkward Middle Child That Needs Desperate Attention. In *BRAC* (Issue September).
- Unesco. (2011). *Enhancing Learning of Children From Diverse Language Backgrounds : Mother Tongue Based Bilingual*.
- Usman, A. M. (2019). The challenges of learning English as a second language and how to solve them. *EIMJ*, 1–17.